

Model-based and empirical analyses of stochastic
fluctuations in economy and finance

DISSERTATION

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Part I
Introduction

1 Introduction

The scientific, financial and technological progresses in the past decades led to an emergent understanding of complex systems [1, 2]. In many domains scientists realized that the development of new ideas requires to grasp concepts originating from research on complex behaviors. Complexity has shown to be a link between many disciplines in science and thus become a ubiquitous interdisciplinary field of study. As a result, discovering and realizing applications of complex systems shed light on a wide variety of fields and endeavors [3, 4].

Complex systems are those in which many different parts are interacting simultaneously and non-linearly with each other, which is responsible for new collective phenomena, usually exhibiting chaotic and emergent behaviors. The basic mechanisms of climate, earthquake, human brain and financial markets exhibit features of complex and collective behaviors occurring in real life [5, 6]. One of the main goals of the analyses of such systems is the manifestation of the spontaneous change of properties in temporal and spatial structures. Moreover, in a complex system the interaction among components occurs in such a way, that the system as a whole cannot be fully described by analyzing each single constituent of the system. Interactions lead to situations, in which the system can show new behavior and possesses properties, which are dissimilar from the behavior and properties of its components. Such systems often act under conditions far from equilibrium and may be influenced by their memory. Another characteristics of complex systems is that they are usually open, i.e. the interactions not only exist between the components of the system but also with its environment [7].

As a perfect example of man-made complex systems, in the present thesis, financial and economic systems are under consideration. Such systems exhibit features typical of complex behavior discussed above [8]: In financial markets there exists a large number of participants with various activities. A large number of agents, banks, companies and their mutual evolving networks provide an appropriate ground for the investigation of complexity and randomness. The financial markets are certainly an open system and continuously interact with political systems, science, agriculture, technology, etc. Moreover, the financial and economic systems are characterized by the dynamics of supply and demand, that means the process can not be in equilibrium. In addition, the financial markets exhibit a long term memory effect and are significantly influenced by their history [9].

Furthermore, the discipline of statistical mechanics, based on probability theory, in theoretical physics opened a new avenue for better understanding of complexity. More precisely, probability theory is applied to explore the behavior of mechanical systems by analyzing

the uncertainties of the states of the system. In particular, the first victorious effort to understand the complex behavior was the development of equilibrium thermodynamics, which allowed to extract the properties of macroscopic systems and describe their behavior in terms of only a few emergent macroscopic properties entering state functions and laws [10]. The discovery of the laws of thermodynamics played a seminal role for describing the macroscopic behavior of various systems beyond ordinary thermodynamics [11]-[15].

One of the main objectives in statistical mechanics is to deal with the properties of large systems, represented by ensembles, including many degrees of freedom, by providing exact methods to connect the macroscopic and microscopic properties. The main reason for our need of statistical methods, stems from the lack of our knowledge of the gigantic number of microscopic degrees of freedom. As a result, the purpose of statistical mechanics is to invent methods to deal with this complexity and incompletely known systems.

One of the inspirations that statistical mechanics provides for financial markets stems from various similarities, e.g. a large number of elementary constituents interact in a rather simple manner, often by few body interactions. In fact, in physics there are established models (Ising spin systems, percolation models, interaction networks, etc.) that are built on this property and are used to model economic systems [16, 17]. Such interdisciplinary approaches provide a setting that enables researchers for better understanding various real-life problems, which are mainly based on turn to a new view of complexity.

Another branch, which has an analogy and parallelism with statistical mechanics is information theory. This is another approach, that neatly describes the notion of the information flow, which constructs the structural ground for setting up probability distributions on the basis of fundamental knowledge of uncertainty and information. Shannon in his stunning work introduced entropy as a measure of the uncertainty of the information contents and in his papers [18, 19] he could completely describe the mathematical background of communication theory. The concept of “energy flow” from statistical mechanics was somehow replaced by the notion of “information flow”. Shannon’s communication theory was essential for science, in particular for engineering and technological sectors. In the present thesis, the elements of information theory are considered to analyze the temporal correlations in the financial time series [20].

Nonlinear dynamics has been also devoted to develop methods and tools [21] in different areas (ergodicity, chaos, stochastic processes, etc.) for studying the complex phenomenon, that appears in various natural or man-made systems [22]. Moreover, it is known that the presence of perturbations, artifacts and irregularities in the data introduce nonlinear effects which often occur in complex networks. Therefore in the present thesis also nonlinear effects

and dependencies such as mutual information, Spearman's correlation coefficient, K -nearest neighbor statistics are intensively considered.

Econophysics history dates back to Daniel Bernoulli for his pioneering work, in which he proposed a theory for risk aversion and utility [23]. Notable scientists with a physics background were often awarded prizes in economy, such as F. Black, R. F. Engle and J. Tinbergen. The latter two scientists were honored by the Nobel Prize. J. Tinbergen won the prize for the development of econometric modeling, R. F. Engle for his time varying volatility (ARCH model) and F. Black is known for his well-known Black-Scholes model. Physicists have progressively offered a novel approach to the economic sciences by devising new methods to explain a variety of phenomena, leading to a number of models and stylized facts [24]-[29], just to name a few. Especially, in the past three decades, they intensively studied fluctuations and collective behavior in human-driven dynamics in economy and finance, inspired by the idea, that such systems are usually multi-agent systems similar to many particle systems, with well defined interaction rules. Some notable physicists who have a great impact in the progress of the field are J. P. Bouchaud, R. Cont, J. D. Farmer, L. Pietronero and H. E. Stanley. For a more comprehensive exposition of the field I recommend the book written by J. P. Bouchaud and M. Potters: "Theory of Financial Risk and Derivative Pricing: From Statistical Physics to Risk Management".

* * *

The objective of this thesis is the investigation of *complexity*, *asymmetry*, *stochasticity* and *non-linearity* of the financial and economic systems by using the tools of statistical mechanics and information theory. More precisely, this thesis concerns *statistical-based modeling* and *empirical analyses* with applications in finance, forecasting, production processes and game theory. In these areas the time dependence of probability distributions is of prime interest and can be "measured" or exactly calculated for model systems.

The correlation coefficients and moments are among the useful quantities to describe the dynamics and the correlations between random variables. However, the full investigation can only be achieved if the probability distribution function of the variable is known; its derivation is one of the main focuses of the present thesis. Asymmetry and forecasting of financial time series will be addressed here as well. Moreover, the derivation of stochastic properties of production processes is also intensively under consideration. Furthermore, being motivated by the usefulness and importance of the notion of *volatility*, the empirical (in financial sector) and theoretical analyses (in production process) of it, in the above mentioned areas are of

major consideration. Finally, the exact probability distribution functions for two of the well-known models in game theory, which appear at the intersection of different disciplines, are also derived.

For the more precise discussion, I go through each chapter by presenting the details. The thesis contains five chapters as follows: The first chapter is the introduction part. In the second chapter I review some mathematical and numerical tools that are relevant to the analyses done in the thesis. The third, fourth and fifth chapters I comment on below in detail.

Part I

In the third chapter I investigate the correlated structure of financial time series and attempt to unveil the fine structure of volatility, based on empirical analysis.

The recent financial crises and risk portfolios require a better understanding of financial market dynamics. One of the important challenges in finance is to forecast the financial market volatility, which has an important meaning for portfolio management and risk measurement (e.g. if the volatilities are predicted to be high for a given asset, then the investors may reduce their commitments to the asset, in order to avoid risk). It is well known that fluctuations in equity prices traded on any stock exchange are weakly correlated, and hardly allow any non-trivial forecasting. This is different for the amplitudes of these fluctuations, namely for volatilities. With some modern options it is possible to make profits with forecasts for volatilities (although forecasts of signed fluctuations would be more easy to turn into money, if they were possible), whence volatilities have been studied extensively in the econometric literature [30, 31].

As first shown in [32], the statistics of volatilities is not uniform. Rather, there is a marked daily structure, with high volatility during the opening hour of the market and a more calm period around noon. Also, equity prices at the opening of the trading session are in general different from the closing prices on the previous trading day, showing that there is a non-trivial overnight dynamics.

The general consensus seems that overnight volatility is useful for predicting subsequent intraday volatility [33]-[35]. This is an important result. But prediction involves a model (GARCH [36], SEMIFAR [37], or different versions of the stochastic volatility model (SVM) [38]-[40]), and none of the papers cited above reported *model independent* analyses of the raw data themselves. This is so in spite of the fact that data analyses that are not involving any model and using only elementary methods and minimal assumptions would be most useful

for understanding the *data* and *basic mechanism(s)* underlying the phenomena, which is the purpose of the analyses in the third chapter. Such analyses based on raw data will allow us to understand the relationships between different observed quantities in order to perform data based predictions.

One of the main concerns in the third chapter of the thesis is with cross-correlations between intraday and overnight volatilities. Due to strong non-stationarity in the data, the analyses are based on different approaches, namely linear (Pearson) and non-linear methods (Spearman, mutual and KNN statistics). For example, the Spearman's correlation coefficients, being based on rank statistics, are known to be much more robust.

I will discuss the finding of a quite stunning time asymmetry in the short time cross correlations between intraday and overnight volatilities (absolute values of log-returns of stock prices). While overnight volatility is significantly (and positively) correlated with the intraday volatility during the following day (allowing thus non-trivial predictions), it is much less correlated with the intraday volatility during the preceding day. While the effect is not unexpected in view of previous observations, its robustness and extreme simplicity are remarkable. The work has been published in [20]. (For the empirical part, the time series of stock prices in different countries are used).

At first sight this strong asymmetry looks very strange, in particular since time asymmetry is usually considered to be very weak in financial data. Many popular models (most noticeably all models of the ARCH family) are time symmetric by construction, and where time asymmetry is seen [41] it is only seen in very special observable. But the findings are indeed compatible with previous analyses [37]-[44].

The asymmetry found in this thesis is also interesting and arguable for the risk management by considering larger time scales and by comparing day/night to night/day results between more distant nights and days. It is remarkable that an extensive statistical study of intraday and overnight returns and volatilities was recently made in [45], but since that analysis was not guided by any theoretical considerations, the finding described above was missed.

Furthermore, the analyses have been done by taking into account foreign markets in different time zones by considering Asian, American and European markets. For the applied content, I used mainly free database downloaded from yahoo finance website [46]. Moreover, in this thesis I analyze the sentiment index presented on Boerse Stuttgart website [47] and also VIX index reported by Chicago Board Options Exchange (CBOE) [48], which are based on the *Sentiment* and *Fear* index of traders and investors. The discussion will be followed by analyzing the predictive power of VIX which tracks the Standard & Poor's 500 U.S. stock market index. Finally, it is worthwhile to mention that the motivation of such analyses comes

from the concept of *self-fulfilling prophecy*, which states that humans with their expectations can influence and control some dynamics.

Part II

The study of fluctuations and collective phenomena in human-driven dynamics is one of the main goals of the fourth chapter, which describes a stochastic model, where the action of many interacting components is presented by random noise. I study here a model-based analyses and stochastic properties of the volatility of the cumulative production based on the experience curve hypothesis.

The concept of experience curve and its empirical evidence were presented in Wright's [49] seminal paper, in which he first discovered the relationship of experience and quantity of the products. Wright's curve is known in the literature as a "learning curve", since it is based on "the more learning by more producing hypothesis", for describing the price-experience relationship. Otherwise said, the higher the experience in producing a specific product is, the lower its production costs are, when the inflation is factored out. More precisely, the learning curve states that the empirically reduction of cost follows a constant proportion rate, as the production duplicates.

The motivation of the analyses of this part comes from the fact that the experience curve effect can be observed in any business, any industry, and any cost element [50]. The learning curve is a way for measuring production efficiency, to forecast production costs and to predict the future prices. As a result, the study of the effect is important, for instance for reducing costs in the production process, which also can lead to lower prices of products in the market. Some researchers discuss its usefulness for forecasting and planning the deployment of industrial and technological activities [51]-[56]. Especially in [51] by using historical data a method for making distributional forecasts is progressively developed.

Despite the wide variety of empirical evidence of the experience curves, there is a lack of theoretical framework of the concept. Motivated by this fact I present here the mathematical framework for describing a relationship between the volatility of cumulative production and the volatility of production (experience) itself. In analogy to the concept of learning curves, which is a relation between the input and the output of a learning process, one of the main findings shows the recursion relation between previous and next probability distribution functions of the system, which characterize their volatility. Knowing distribution functions of the cumulative production and its volatility can describe the marketing and movement of products. Also it will allow us to calculate various quantities, such as mean, variance, higher order moments and price volatility correlation.

In the first part of investigations, by using the steepest descent method, for a model system the volatility of cumulative production for the narrow distribution of noise is calculated. To explain this finding the stochastic properties of cumulative production are studied, by assuming that production is a geometric random walk and empirically cumulative production growth follows a smooth exponential behavior in the presence of noise. The result is stunning and potentially powerful. Also it is tested for 51 products and technologies and the agreement is pretty good [51]. In the long time limit, the results show that cumulative production grows at the same rate as production, and the volatility of this growth rate is lower than the volatility of production. This is due to the fact that production tends to grow exponentially, so that cumulative production tends to grow exponentially with lower fluctuations. The investigation of cumulative production is a key parameter here and by considering the experience curve as a time series model, a mathematical framework for the volatility of the time series is derived. The finding can lead to the prediction of the volatility of cumulative production based on the volatility of experience or production. The work has been published in [51].

In the further course of this chapter, the generalization of the above analysis is carried through: The first part, described above, addressed the effects of narrow, normally distributed noise in the production process. Due to its wide applicability in industrial and technological activities and motivated by the fact that there exists a large number of cases where the distribution describing a underlying phenomenon is not Gaussian, (e.g. the price fluctuations of most financial assets [31]), the mathematical foundation for an *arbitrary* distribution function of the process is also presented, which is expected to pave the future research on forecasting of the production process. As a consequence of the generalization of the method, the results yield a systematic control over the validity of the finding obtained for the narrow distributions discussed above. More precisely, in the present work, a recursion relation of integral type that replaces simulations by highly accurate numerical integration is derived. The results show how different types of noise affect the cumulative production within the model, based on the learning by doing hypothesis. The work has been published in [57]. Finally, higher order moments such as skewness and kurtosis of the process will be addressed as well.

The method of the work used for the production process, can be applied also to different domains [58]-[62], especially it can characterize the descriptor of a risk measure [63], which is one of the main challenges in finance. In fact, with the same approach and analogy, in the present thesis, the computation of the capital from investment by depreciation, based on the perpetual inventory method in economy is presented. (Note that the perpetual inventory method is concerned with the estimation of the net capital from the cumulative capital stock,

the analysis of annual depreciation, etc [64]).

Part III

The study of probability is considered in many domains and dates back to the seventeenth century. One of the fields which is very closely related to it, is the gambling and game theory [65]: from dice to risk benefit analysis, i.e. “games of chance” is composed of random events and variables. Motivated by this fact, in the fifth chapter of this thesis I study Parrondo’s games [66]-[71], which exhibit interesting phenomena at the intersection of game theory, statistical finance and physics, see [71] for interdisciplinary applications.

Parrondo’s paradox states that playing two losing games in a random or periodic order can result in a winning outcome [66]-[81]. Of course, the opposite situation is also possible; a random combination of two winning games can give a losing game. Parrondo invented a game-theoretic model of a Brownian flashing ratchet [72]-[78], thus producing a discrete-time model of the ratchet effect [66]. In the case of Brownian ratchets, a particle moves in a potential, which randomly changes between two versions. For each there is a detailed balance condition. However, for random switches between the two potentials, there is on average a directed motion. This phenomenon is fundamentally related to portfolio optimization [81], and corresponds to the “volatility pumping” strategy in portfolio optimization. For a two-asset portfolio one half of the capital is kept in the first asset, the other half in the second asset with high volatility [82].

In the present thesis, by using the Fourier transform, the exact probability distribution functions for both the capital dependent and history dependent Parrondo’s games are calculated. In certain cases there are found strong oscillations near the maximum of the probability distribution with two limiting distributions for odd and even number of rounds of the game. Parrondo’s paradox is also used in financial risk management by revealing the statement, that losing strategies combined and can turn into a winning strategy. So the investigation of Parrondo strategies is useful for instance for cases in which declining birth and harmful processes combine in a beneficial way.

Especially intriguing is an anti-Parrondo effect or *Verschlimmbesserung* where reduced confidence in a measurement results from an increase in the number of observations that are in agreement [83]. The Parrondo’s games have been also applied in [84, 85] as a toy model for studying the dynamics in the stock market and in [86], it has been illustrated a Parrondo-like model for switching between poor performing investments. The stochastic and universal portfolio models [87, 88] are also closely related to Parrondo’s model. Later other modifications of the games were invented such as the two-envelope problem and the Allison mixture [89]

where random mixing of two random sequences creates autocorrelation [90]. In the further course of this PhD work, the exact probability distribution functions of the two-envelope problem are also derived. Here, we will give an integral representation for the exact probability distribution of the model, then calculate both the mean capital growth rate and variance of the capital distribution after a large number of games. The work has been published in [91].

For applications it is most important to find the capital growth rate and the variance of the distribution. This is the reason that the present thesis not only deals with a few characteristics of the model, but with the exact distribution function and its asymptotic behavior. The existence of degenerate largest eigenvalues of the time evolution creates oscillations in the probability distribution of the capital and results in the existence of two limiting distributions. This is a typical situation with real data of stock fluctuations in financial markets, and surprisingly it is explained by a simple model in the present thesis. The method of the work can be applied to Brownian ratchets, molecular motors and portfolio optimization. The work has been published in [79].

I begin below with technical explanations of the above statements by exploring the realm of this field by examples. In the further discussion I switch to “we”, since I include here much material from the published work, which resulted from collaborations by being in different places such as Max-Planck Institute for the Physics of Complex Systems, Dresden, Germany (Prof. Holger Kantz); Jülich Research Center Germany (Prof. Peter Grassberger); Mathematical Institute of University of Oxford and Institute for New Economic Thinking at the Oxford Martin School, UK (Prof. J. Doyne Farmer); Sapienza University of Rome, Italy (Prof. Luciano Pietronero) and Physics department of University of Wuppertal, Germany (Prof. Andreas Klümper).

Part II

Review of some mathematical and numerical tools

2 Review of some mathematical and numerical tools

In the present thesis quantities based on probability distributions are of prime interest, which can be measured either numerically or calculated analytically. For completeness we first review in detail several tools of statistical dependencies between random variables used in this thesis.

The correlation tools were invented for measuring the degree of relationship between two random variables. In data analysis, one of the important goals for using the correlation is to perform data based predictions. In case of correlation between two random variables, the knowledge of one of them, by using adequate tools, allows to predict the value of the other random variable. Here we discuss Pearson's and Spearman's correlation coefficients.

The powerful tools such as Fourier transformation, convolution and the steepest descent method, are described in detail as well. In this chapter we review also the elements of information theory, such as mutual information, entropy, conditional mutual information, etc. For the numerical part we thoroughly analyze two useful methods, namely the histogram and the K -nearest neighbor statistics. In particular, in this thesis these statistical tools are utilized for estimating the mutual information, which in turn serves for analyzing the correlated structure of financial time series. In the Appendix, one can find the programs for the analysis of mutual information, written in Matlab, considering the autoregressive time series.

2.1 Pearson's correlation coefficient

The Pearson's correlation coefficient is a measure of linear dependency between two random variables and for the random variables X and Y is given by the following expression:

$$\rho_{X,Y} = \frac{E[XY] - E[X]E[Y]}{\sqrt{E[X^2] - [E[X]]^2} \sqrt{E[Y^2] - [E[Y]]^2}}, \quad (1)$$

where E denotes the expectation value.

In the literature, the formula can be found often written as follows:

$$\rho_{X,Y} = \frac{cov(X, Y)}{\sigma_X \sigma_Y}, \quad (2)$$

where $cov(X, Y) = E[XY] - E[X]E[Y]$ is the covariance between random variables and σ_X , σ_Y are the standard deviations of X and Y , respectively. So, the Pearson's correlation coefficient implies a normalized covariance of the two random variables.

Pearson's correlation coefficient is mostly used for sample data statistics. One of the nice properties of Pearson's correlation coefficient is its invariant feature under a change of scale

of the two random variables [92].

Due to our interest in time series analysis of stock markets, it is useful to introduce also the autocorrelation, which is a function of time delay. This is one of the typical measures for finding for instance repeating phenomena between observations with respect to time lag.

One can measure autocorrelation by considering the values of the process at different time domains and by using the above defined Pearson's correlation coefficient. Otherwise said, in case when we are dealing with the Pearson's correlation between values of the random process at different times, then one speaks about autocorrelation of the random process and between times s and t is defined as

$$\rho_{t,s} = \frac{E[(X_t - \mu_t)(X_s - \mu_s)]}{\sigma_t \sigma_s}, \quad (3)$$

where we supposed the process has mean μ_t and variance σ_t^2 at time t and the mean μ_s and the variance σ_s^2 at the time s respectively.

If we consider a stationary process, in which the mean μ and the variance σ^2 are time independent, then the autocorrelation between two different points in the X_t stationary process is defined as follows:

$$\rho_\tau = \frac{E[(X_t - \mu)(X_{t+\tau} - \mu)]}{\sigma^2}.$$

Thus, for the stationary processes the autocorrelation is a function of the time difference between two points. Trend stationary and autoregressive processes are typical examples of models with autocorrelation. The latter process will be discussed later in detail.

2.2 Spearman's correlation coefficient

Pearson's correlation coefficient can also be used by considering rank statistics of data. In this case the obtained correlation coefficient is called Spearman. Phrased in simple words, if we want to deal with the Spearman's correlation coefficient we need to convert the scores to the ranked data and apply the Pearson's correlation coefficient formula to the set of ranks.

The Pearson's correlation shows the degree of linear relationship between two variables, whereas the Spearman's correlation is a good choice for measuring the consistency of the relationship, including nonlinear effects; also it is an appropriate measurement tool, for studying highly skewed or kurtotic distributions.

Especially the Spearman's correlation gives a better result, if the data has outliers, which is typical in financial time series, whereas the Pearson's correlation coefficient is not sensitive to the effect of outliers. This statement comes from the fact that Spearman's coefficient limits the values of outliers to the value of their ranks.

Spearman's coefficient is a measure of the monotonic relationship between two variables. We like to note, that in a monotonic case we have strictly increasing or decreasing, but not mixed relation. Every time when X increases by the same increment of the amount of Y , then the correlation is perfectly consistent and the data points fit perfectly on a straight line. In a case of an increasingly negative monotonic relationship, X increases in rank when Y decreases. (Note that the amount of increase (decrease) of the variables might not be the same). A positive (negative) Spearman coefficient indicates an increasing (decreasing) monotonic relationship between X and Y .

When two random variables are consistently related to each other, their ranks will be linearly related to each other. Let us interpret this statement through an example. In a perfectly consistent positive relationship, when the variable X increases, the Y variable is also increasing. That means the smallest value of X corresponds to the smallest value of Y . We observe the same for other values. This means that the rank of X and Y increase consistently. As a consequence, the ranks are linearly related to each other, i.e. we observe a perfect fit on a straight line. In other words, each increase in X is followed by an increase in Y , although the relationship can be non-linear. This example illustrates that a consistent relationship between variables creates a linear relationship, when the values of the variables are converted to their ranks. Based on this, the Pearson's correlation coefficient formula is used for measuring a linear relationship considering the ranked data.

Spearman's correlation coefficient is nonparametric, that means, it does not make any assumption on the distribution of the sample data. On the other hand when both variables are normally distributed the use of the Spearman's correlation coefficient does not give any additional information.

Based on rank statistics Spearman's correlation coefficient is known to be more robust and also insensitive to the difference between raw data. These statements will be discussed more precisely in the next chapter by revealing them through financial time series analysis.

For obtaining the Spearman's correlation coefficient, one can also transform the data X and Y to a uniform distribution and then calculate the Pearson's correlation coefficient between them.

There are two methods to calculate Spearman's correlation coefficient. As discussed above, it can be obtained with the same formula as Pearson's, by converting the observations of stochastic variables X and Y to their ranks $r = \text{rg}X$ and $s = \text{rg}Y$ in the sample as follows:

$$\rho_{r,s} = \frac{E[rs] - E[r]E[s]}{\sqrt{E[r^2] - E[r]^2} \sqrt{E[s^2] - E[s]^2}}.$$

Let us organize the data of n observations of X and Y random variables. If the data does not have tied ranks (all ranks are unique) it is convenient to use the following expression:

$$\rho_{r,s} = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_i d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}, \quad (4)$$

where $d_i = r_i - s_i$ is the difference between paired ranks. In this formula the Spearman's correlation coefficient is calculated by the ratio of the sum of the squared differences in the ranks of the paired data values, to the number of variables pairs. There are different ways to prove this formula, for example, by considering the Pearson's correlation coefficient formula applied to a sample and by keeping in mind that ρ is invariant under changes in location and scale of the variables. Note that in the case of tied ranks, formula (4) is not valid.

2.3 Fourier transform

As discussed above, one of the core and important investigations in this thesis is the study of probability distribution functions for different problems in economy. Knowing the distribution function of the underlying quantity and phenomenon, tells us a lot about the system under consideration. One of the tools that frequently is used in probability theory and its application is the so called Fourier transformation.

The Fourier transform of functions is known to be very useful for instance for solving linear problems with some kind of translational invariance and may serve as characteristic function for stochastic distributions.

The Fourier representation of a function $f : R \rightarrow C$ and its Fourier transform $F(k)$ are given by:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(k) e^{ikx} dk, \quad (5)$$

$$F(k) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) e^{-ikx} dx. \quad (6)$$

The integral in Eq. (5) is also called the inverse Fourier transform. The approach has many applications in mathematical science, physics and engineering: for example the Fourier transform is widely used in the study of quantum mechanics, signal processing and wave propagation [93]. In this work, this powerful tool will be used for finding the exact probability distribution functions of important models in game theory and financial risk, the so called Parrondo's games, which we defer to chapter five.

In analogy to Eqs. (5) and (6), for the case of functions in $(-L, L)$ intervals with periodic boundary conditions there exist the following expressions:

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} F_n e^{\frac{in\pi x}{L}}, \quad (7)$$

$$F_n = \frac{1}{2L} \int_{-L}^L f(x) e^{-\frac{in\pi x}{L}} dx, \quad (8)$$

where F_n are called the Fourier coefficients.

The Fourier transform is also useful for the calculation of moments. It is known that the moments of the distribution functions are given by

$$m_n = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^n f(x) dx,$$

where the moments of $f(x)$ are derived through successive derivatives as follows:

$$m_n = (-i)^n \frac{d^n}{dk^n} F(k) \Big|_{k=0}. \quad (9)$$

Due to this equation the Fourier transform $F(k)$ is also known as the characteristic function. Since $f(x)$ is normalized, one always has $F(0) = 1$ and therefore we have the $m_0 = 1$ normalization condition. From the theoretical point of view the knowledge of all moments is equivalent to the knowledge of the distribution function.

Another important quantity is the cumulant, which is defined from the characteristic function as follows:

$$c_n = (-i)^n \frac{d^n}{dk^n} \log F(k) \Big|_{k=0}. \quad (10)$$

Similarly to mean and variance, one of the nice features of cumulants is their additivity, i.e. for independent random variables the cumulant of the sum is given by the sum of the individual cumulants. This stems from the fact that by multiplying the characteristic functions, their logarithm add. The additivity of cumulants simply follows from the linearity of the derivative.

Since the Gaussian distribution is ubiquitous it is also worthwhile to mention that for this distribution all cumulants of order larger than two are zero.

2.4 Convolution

The Convolution is a mathematical tool, which maps two functions to a new function. The convolution is the integral of the product of the two functions after one is reversed and shifted and is given by the following expression:

$$(f * g)(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\tau) g(x - \tau) d\tau = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x - \tau) g(\tau) d\tau. \quad (11)$$

The applications of convolution can be seen in different domains, such as probability, statistics, finance and for solving differential equations. Hence we are interested in its application

to the calculation of the distribution function for the sum of independent random variables, let us discuss this through an example: If we denote the variation of the price of an asset between this month and the next month by Δ_X and similarly between the next subsequent months by Δ_Y , then one may ask what the distribution of the total variation of the asset price within the whole period could be. Let us suppose that these two variables are distributed according to some independent distributions $P_1(\Delta_X)$ and $P_2(\Delta_Y)$. As a matter of fact, the distribution of the sum of these two random variables is given by the following equation, which is simply the convolution of the respective distributions:

$$P(x) = P_1 * P_2 = \int P_1(\tau)P_2(x - \tau)d\tau. \quad (12)$$

One can generalize the concept to n independent random variables and get the following expression:

$$P(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P_1(\tau_1)P_2(\tau_2)\dots P_n(\tau_n)\delta\left(x - \sum_{j=1}^n \tau_j\right) d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \dots d\tau_n, \quad (13)$$

which simply owes to the characteristics of independently distributed random variables. The special case, Eq. (12) arises for $n = 2$ and by integrating out τ_2 .

It is worthwhile to mention the convolution theorem, which states that the Fourier transform of a convolution is the product of Fourier transforms. The statement is true for various Fourier-related transforms and can be expressed as:

$$F(f * g) = F(f) \cdot F(g),$$

where $F(f)$ and $F(g)$ are the Fourier transforms of f and g functions respectively.

The transition of the convolution to the pointwise product is very useful, especially for performing numerical analysis; while for the convolution one should tackle with $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ orders, this formula supports to reduce the quadratic order to $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$, which helps to implement an algorithm faster.

Finally, in the further course of the thesis, this valuable tool will be used for finding the relationship between the cumulative production and the production itself (in a presence of noise), by analyzing their probability distribution functions and volatilities.

2.5 Steepest descent or saddle point method

The saddle point method described, e.g. in [93, 94] presents an approximation formula for any *narrow* probability distribution function. The essence of the saddle point method is to approximate the integral by taking into account only that portion of the range of the integration where the integrand takes large values.

The method is a powerful approach for considering the large k asymptotic of integrals of the form:

$$I(k) = \int_C f(z)e^{k\phi(z)} dz, \quad (14)$$

where $f(z)$ and $\phi(z) \in \mathcal{C}$ are analytical functions of z .

The idea of the approach is based on the application of the analyticity of the integrand by changing the contour C to a new contour C' where $\phi(z)$ has an imaginary part, which is a constant. That means the Eq. (14) becomes:

$$I(k) = e^{ikv} \int_{C'} f(z)e^{ku(z)} dz, \quad (15)$$

where $\phi(z) = u + iv$.

Considering the fact that $\phi(z)$ is analytic and v is constant on C' , the derivative of u perpendicular to C' is also zero. Therefore along this path C' , the increase of u is maximal (path of steepest ascent) or the decrease of u is maximal (path of steepest descent). For the calculation of the integral we utilize the latter one, therefore the method is called steepest descent. The path of the steepest descent includes a point z^* for which $\phi'(z^*) = 0$. Such a point is called saddle point and therefore the method is often called the saddle point method. The idea is to deform the contour into the steepest descent curve, which includes the saddle point and the contribution near the saddle point is the dominant one. If one deforms the integration contour, the value of integral will remain unchanged and the contour levels of the real part of $\phi(z)$ are everywhere orthogonal to the contour line of the imaginary part of the $\phi(z)$ function. This statement ensures that the imaginary part of $\phi(z)$ is constant. More precisely (by using the above notations), we should deform the contour of integration C into a new integration path C' , so that the new integration path passes through zero(s) of $\phi'(z)$ and that the imaginary part of the $\phi(z)$ is constant.

But this is not always the case and sometimes the contour cannot be deformed into a curve including a saddle point, e.g. if one encounters singularities of the integrand. In practice, the steepest descent method requires the identification of critical points $\phi'(z^*) = 0$ close to the original curve C and to control the occurrence of singularities between C and the steepest descent curve C' .

For large k we have the following result:

$$I(k) \simeq \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{-k\phi''(z^*)}} f(z^*) e^{k\phi(z^*)}.$$

In general, the saddle point of a multivariate function $S = S(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_t)$ is defined by the system of equations $\partial_i S(z^*) = 0$, $\partial_i = \partial/\partial z_i$, $i \in \{1, \dots, t\}$ for which one can write

$$k\phi(z) \equiv S(z) = S(z^*) + \sum_{ij} (z_i - z_i^*)(z_j - z_j^*) G_{ij} + \mathcal{O}(\{(z - z^*)^3\}), \quad (16)$$

where z^* is the solution of the saddle point equations and $G_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \partial_i \partial_j S(z)|_{z=z^*}$.

For the further analysis of the method we need to analyze the function around the saddle point, which is a dominant point.

The point z^* is called saddle point of order N if the first N derivatives disappear:

$$\frac{d^m \phi}{dz^m} \Big|_{z=z^*} = 0, \quad m = 1, \dots, N, \quad \frac{d^{N+1} \phi}{dz^{N+1}} \Big|_{z=z^*} \neq 0. \quad (17)$$

The above statements will be more clear for the reader by following the calculations in the fourth chapter for two analytical expressions. This powerful method will be used here for the analysis of stochastic properties of cumulative production in a presence of narrow distribution of noise. The investigation leads to an important result in the production process, which we defer to chapter 4. In the fifth chapter the method is also employed for obtaining elementary and nice expressions in the large time limit, by considering model-based analysis.

2.6 Elements and quantities of information theory

Information theory sheds light on many problems that have been troubling communication engineers and scientists for years. It provides a universal tool for measuring the amount of information based on uncertainty and knowledge of the underlying system. The words communication and information are important for all of us and in many domains the tools of information theory can be used. Indeed, it has a broad scope in areas, such as engineering, statistical physics, mathematics and economy.

The background of information theory dates back to the early 1940, when the researchers thought it is impossible to send information with negligible probability of error. Shannon showed indeed how it is possible to make the probability of error to come to zero for all rates of information below the channel capacity.

The channel capacity is one of the fundamental concepts of information theory. It is exactly the maximum amount at which one can share the information in the channel and have the corresponding information at the output with a low probability of error. If we define the input random variable with X and the output Y , then the capacity C is determined:

$$C = \max I(X, Y), \quad (18)$$

where $I(X, Y)$ is the mutual information between these random variables, which we will comment on in detail later.

According to the above discussion, that means for any information rate $R < C$, it is always possible to transmit information with small error. Contrariwise, for any information rate larger than the channel capacity it is impossible to transmit the information with small error [95]. Mobile phones could be a simple example of a noisy channel for describing the transmission process and while there is noise, it is possible to maximize the rate of information through the channel.

In information theory, the channel coding is exactly aimed to find such codes that can be utilized to transmit data over a noisy channel with a small coding error. In order to describe the transmission and data comparison, the quantities such as entropy, relative entropy, mutual information and conditional mutual information were introduced.

The basic and fundamental quantities of information theory are constructed in terms of probability distributions that underlie the process. Thus, from the mathematical point of view, information theory is closely tied with statistical mechanics and probability theory [96]. Furthermore, since the elements of information theory measure a relationship and dependency between variables, they are appropriate tool for describing correlations between different quantities in different domains such as statistics, automation, physics, biology, economy and finance [95]. In this thesis the application of this elegant theory appears in the latter one,

namely for the study of the dependent structure of financial data. Let us conclude this initial discussion about the information theory by recalling Shannon’s statement from his “The Bandwagon” letter [97], in which he wrote the importance of information theory as follows: “In short, information theory is currently partaking of a somewhat of a heady draught of general popularity”.

In the further course, we review some important quantities and elements of the information theory.

2.6.1 Entropy

Entropy and relative entropy are devised to describe the uncertainty or disorder in the system. Entropy has properties that satisfy the intuitive notion of measuring the information rate, thus it is sometimes called the self-information of a random variable.

Let us introduce the mathematical framework of the entropy, by focusing on discrete random variables, since in the thesis the application will be to real valued time series. According to Shannon the entropy of a discrete random variable X with a probability function $p(x)$ is defined by:

$$H(X) = - \sum_x p(x) \log p(x). \quad (19)$$

From the above definition, it is clear that the entropy is a non-linear functional of the probability distribution of the random variable. The entropy is non-negative and is measured in bits or nats (the base of the logarithm defines the unit of measurement). As it is clear from its notion, if there is no uncertainty of the outcome of the event, then the entropy is simply zero.

If we consider that the discrete random variable X has $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ values, then the upper bound of the entropy is $H(X) \leq \log(n)$.

Furthermore, the entropy is characterized by the following properties:

- Continuity: The amount of change in probabilities is proportional to the amount of change in the entropy.
- Symmetry: The outcome is invariant under a permutation of the x_i ’s.
- Maximum: The entropy is maximum, if all events occur with the same probability.
- Additivity: For independent subsystems (or if the interactions between them are known) the entropy of a whole system is characterized by the sums of the entropies of all subsystems [98].

Let us now extend the definition of entropy of a single variable to a pair of random variables. The joint entropy $H(X, Y)$ of a pair of discrete random variables X and Y is defined as follows:

$$H(X, Y) = - \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log p(x, y), \quad (20)$$

where $p(x, y)$ is the joint probability distribution function of the pair of random variables. Note that for simplicity we use everywhere the following sloppy notation for the marginal probabilities: $p_x(x) \rightarrow p(x)$.

The relationship between joint and marginal probability distributions is defined by: $p(x) = \sum_y p(x, y)$ and the conditional probability $p(x|y)$ is expressed by the joint and marginal probabilities as follows: $p(x, y) = p(x|y)p(y)$.

Another important quantity is the conditional entropy $H(X|Y)$, which is the entropy of a random variable conditioned on the knowledge of another variable and is given by the following relation:

$$H(X|Y) = - \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log p(x|y). \quad (21)$$

Finally the relationship between joint and conditional entropy is given by the following expression:

$$H(X, Y) = H(Y) + H(X|Y). \quad (22)$$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} H(X, Y) &= - \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log p(x, y) \\ &= - \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log [p(x|y) p(y)] \\ &= - \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log p(y) - \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log p(x|y). \end{aligned}$$

Using the relationship between joint and marginal distribution discussed above and also from Eq. (21) we obtain

$$H(X, Y) = - \sum_y p(y) \log p(y) - \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log p(x|y) = H(Y) + H(X|Y).$$

2.6.2 Mutual Information, relative entropy and conditional mutual information

One of the reasons for the intensive investigations of mutual information (MI) is its theoretical background [96]. Furthermore, as mentioned above, mutual information in contrast to the linear correlation coefficient is efficient for studying dependencies that include non-linearity and do not exhibit themselves in the covariance.

The mutual information shows the amount of information that one random variable contains about another. More precisely, mutual information is the reduction of the uncertainty of one random variable due to the information content of another random variable.

Let us now define the MI's mathematical framework, which is based on the notion of entropy and is given by the following expression:

$$I(X, Y) = \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log \frac{p(x, y)}{p(x)p(y)}. \quad (23)$$

From the above definition, it is obvious that the mutual information is symmetric in X and Y , i.e. $I(X, Y) = I(Y, X)$ and due to Jensen's inequality it is always non-negative. From the mathematical and intuitive notion of the concept, it is clear that the mutual information is only zero if the two random variables are independent. The latter statement is also true for quantities based on Renyi entropies [99]. However mutual information is particular in its notion and mathematical background.

For obtaining a better understanding of the mutual information let us express it by entropies. We can rewrite equation (23) as

$$I(X, Y) = \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log \frac{p(x|y)}{p(x)} = \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log p(x|y) - \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log p(x).$$

By use of Eqs. (19), (21) and the relationship between marginal and joint distributions we obtain

$$I(X, Y) = H(X) - H(X|Y).$$

This relation between mutual information and the entropies of the variables explicitly shows that the mutual information describes the reduction of uncertainties due to the knowledge of other variables, in this case Y .

We discussed above that in case of two independent random variables the mutual information is zero. Indeed, Eq. (23) shows this statement, since in this case we can rewrite the joint entropy as $p(x, y) = p(x) \cdot p(y)$ and we get a $\log 1 = 0$ identity. This statement also follows directly from the intuitive notion and definition of mutual information, which quantifies the

amount of information that two random variables share among each other. Given this, it is clear that if the variables are independent, then information about one of them does not give any knowledge about the other. On the other hand if X and Y are related to each other, as a deterministic function, there is a share of information between them. In the extreme case, where $X=Y$ we have

$$I(X, X) = H(X) - H(X|X) = H(X).$$

This equation tells us that the mutual information of a random variable with itself is simply equal to the entropy of the variable.

Mutual information appears to be a special case of a more general quantity called relative entropy or Kullback–Leibler entropy, which is a measure of the difference or “distance” between two probability distributions. If we denote the probabilities by q and p , the Kullback–Leibler entropy is defined as follows:

$$D(p||q) = \sum_x p(x) \log \frac{p(x)}{q(x)}. \quad (24)$$

Like the mutual information it is always non-negative and diverges if and only if $p = q$.

It is worthwhile also to define the conditional mutual information, which describes a reduction of uncertainty in X based on the knowledge of Y when Z is given and is defined as follows:

$$I(X; Y|Z) = \sum_z p(z) \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y|z) \log \frac{p(x, y|z)}{p(x|z)p(y|z)}. \quad (25)$$

As a matter of fact, the conditional mutual information is the expectation value of mutual information of two random variables conditioned on the third and for discrete random variables X, Y and Z it is always non-negative.

Similar to the mutual information we can express the conditional mutual information through entropies:

$$I(X; Y|Z) = H(X|Z) - H(X|Y, Z).$$

As a result the relationship between mutual and conditional mutual information is given by

$$I(X; Y|Z) = I(X; Y, Z) - I(X, Z).$$

2.7 Histogram method

The histogram or binning method is a statistical technique, which proposes a multivariate histogram for the estimation of the probabilities and was first introduced by Pearson [100]. The approach has a long history and it is the most common and widespread method for the estimation of the density of probability function.

For the construction of a histogram the sample space is divided into a number of bins. The idea of the method is based on counting the points in different bins. Let us denote by $n_x(i)$ the number of points of variable X falling into the i th bin and consequently $n_y(j)$ shows the number of points of variable Y falling into the j th bin. Furthermore, $n_{x,y}(i, j)$ indicates the number of points that fall into the bin i th as well as into the bin j th; these points result from the intersection and joint realization of the data points. The idea is to approximate the density of the probability function by the fraction of points, that fall into the corresponding bin.

Let us consider X and Y random variables, with the marginal $p_x = \int dy p(x, y)$ and $p_y = \int dx p(x, y)$ density functions and use the histogram approach for the estimation of mutual information. For the finite sum equation (23) approximately can be written:

$$I(X, Y) \approx I_{binned}(X, Y) \equiv \sum_{ij} p(i, j) \log \frac{p_{x,y}(i, j)}{p_x(i)p_y(j)}, \quad (26)$$

where $p_x(i) = \int_i dx p(x)$, $p_y(j) = \int_j dy p(y)$ and $p(i, j) = \int_i \int_j dx dy p(x, y)$. (We closely follow the notation used in [101]).

We consider N bivariate measurements, which are assumed to be independent identically distributed (iid) realizations of a random variable. After normalization, for the marginal and joint probabilities we have: $p_x(i) \approx n_x(i)/N$, $p_y(j) \approx n_y(j)/N$ and $p(i, j) \approx n_{x,y}(i, j)/N$. In the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$ indeed from the right hand side of Eq. (26) we get the MI for X and Y variables.

$I(X, Y)$ in (26) is weakly dependent on the binning if the distribution of (X, Y) is rather two dimensional and continuous, i.e. if it is well approximated by a continuous $p(x, y)$. In the other extreme case, where $X = Y$, then the mutual information is binning dependent. In 2.6.2 we discussed that for this extreme case the mutual information is equal to the entropy of the variable: $I_{binned} = -\sum_i p_i \log p_i$. If we consider that X has a uniform distribution in $[0, 1]$, M bins and $p_i = \frac{1}{M}$, then the mutual information $I(X, X) = \ln M$ is a function of the bin size, e.g. a coarse graining from M to $M/2$ bins does not leave the mutual information invariant, it reduces its value by $\log 2$.

There is no need to take a similar size for all bins, rather some estimators [102, 103] are flexible with regard to the bin size. Although such estimators are better than estimators with fixed bin size, there are still systematic errors by approximating the probabilities with

the frequency ratios and also by discretizing mutual information. Nevertheless, this error could be minimized [104] for the finite size corrections.

While the histogram method is easy to grasp, it has several disadvantages: It is discrete and changes with the choice of the initial parameters and bin width. Even when using the same bin size, different initial conditions may change the histogram completely, e.g. the discontinuities of the estimation are an artifact of the chosen bin locations. Otherwise said, we often observe bins with large filling and on the other hand bins that remain empty. Another problem is the dimensionality, because the number of bins grows exponentially with the number of dimensions. Due to these artifacts the histogram method is not appropriate for the advanced level of analyses and therefore we study another method called *K*-nearest neighbor statistics, which we will comment on in the next section.

There are also other estimators, such as kernel density [105, 106], which are related to histograms, but they have properties such as continuity by a suitable choice of the kernel. Furthermore, the kernel density estimators are particularly advantageous when the data set is small.

2.8 *K*-nearest neighbor statistics

Here we discuss the *K*-nearest neighbor statistics (KNN) for the estimation of mutual information presented in [101], which in contrast to the above described histogram method is data efficient, adaptive and has minimal bias. The approach is non-parametric, that means it does not make any assumption on the distribution of the underlying data.

Let us consider metrics on the spaces underlying X , Y and $Z = (X, Y)$. The distance between the fixed point and its neighbors is denoted by $d_{i,j} = \|z_i - z_j\|$ and the maximum norm for the space Z is

$$\|z_i - z_j\| = \max \{ \|x_i - x_j\|, \|y_i - y_j\| \}, \quad (27)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the norms in the spaces underlying X and Y and they can be chosen differently.

We denote the distance from z_i to its K th neighbor by $\frac{\epsilon(i)}{2}$, where K is a positive integer. Similarly $\frac{\epsilon_x(i)}{2}$ and $\frac{\epsilon_y(i)}{2}$ are the distances between the same points projected into X and Y sub-spaces. Obviously $\epsilon(i) = \max\{\epsilon_x(i), \epsilon_y(i)\}$.

The value of the K parameter is significantly important for the performance of the statistics. The notion of *near* is general and the best choice depends on the data and the underlying problem. Typically the value of K is chosen empirically and the parameter with the best result and accuracy is picked up. If $K = 1$, then one speaks about a single nearest neighbor. For the estimation we follow two algorithms: In the first algorithm we consider the number

$n_x(i)$ of points x_j that have a distance to x_i strictly less than $\frac{\epsilon(i)}{2}$ and consequently we follow the same procedure for y .

The formula, that does not require the investigation of probability distribution for the estimation of mutual information is

$$I(X, Y) = \psi(K) - \langle \psi(n_x + 1) + \psi(n_y + 1) \rangle + \psi(N), \quad (28)$$

where ψ is the digamma function and N is the number of points in the entire sample.

In the second algorithm (which we use more frequently) we replace n_x and n_y by the number of points in the respective subspaces:

$$\|x_i - x_j\| \leq \epsilon_x(i)/2 \quad (29)$$

and

$$\|y_i - y_j\| \leq \epsilon_y(i)/2 \quad (30)$$

Finally, the second estimator of MI is

$$I(X, Y) = \psi(K) - 1/K - \langle \psi(n_x) + \psi(n_y) \rangle + \psi(N). \quad (31)$$

Both algorithms work pretty well and give very similar results.

2.9 Analytical example of mutual information

Mutual information can be obtained analytically if we consider normally distributed random variables X and Y with 0 mean, σ_x^2 and $\sigma_y^2 \equiv a^2 \sigma_x^2$ variances and covariance equal to $\sigma_x^2 a^2$, with joint probability $p(x, y)$ and correspondingly marginal probabilities $p(x)$ and $p(y)$. Conditional probability of x conditioned on y is a Gaussian distribution with the mean value y and the variance σ_x^2 . In this case there exists a fully analytical expression [103], which is simple and potentially powerful and is equal to

$$I(X, Y) = -\frac{1}{2} \ln(1 - a^2), \quad (32)$$

where in a limit $a \rightarrow 1$ we have $I(X, Y) \rightarrow \infty$. Let us derive it in detail by recalling the mutual information formula:

$$I(x, y) = \int_{R^2} p(x|y)p(y) \log \frac{p(x|y)p(y)}{p(y)p(x)} dx dy, \quad (33)$$

where the integration is over the entire plane.

For the distribution functions we have the following expressions

$$p(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_x} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_x^2}}, \quad (34)$$

$$p(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}a\sigma_x} e^{-\frac{y^2}{2\sigma_x^2 a^2}}, \quad (35)$$

and

$$p(x|y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_\eta} e^{-\frac{(x-y)^2}{2\sigma_\eta^2}}. \quad (36)$$

For consistency, we need

$$\sigma_x = \frac{\sigma_\eta}{\sqrt{1-a^2}}. \quad (37)$$

For simplicity we replace $\sigma_\eta = 1$ ¹ in Eqs. (34-36) and obtain the following:

$$I(x, y) = \frac{-\sqrt{1-a^2}\log(\sqrt{1-a^2})}{2\pi a} \int e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}+xy-\frac{y^2}{2a^2}} dx dy + \frac{\sqrt{1-a^2}}{2\pi a} \int e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}+xy-\frac{y^2}{2a^2}} \left(\frac{-x^2 a^2}{2} + xy - \frac{y^2}{2} \right) dx dy. \quad (38)$$

Let us consider the components separately: Thus we have

$$I_1 = \frac{-\sqrt{1-a^2}\log(\sqrt{1-a^2})}{2\pi a} \int e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}+xy-\frac{y^2}{2a^2}} dx dy \quad (39)$$

and

$$I_2 = \frac{\sqrt{1-a^2}}{2\pi a} \int e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}+xy-\frac{y^2}{2a^2}} \left(\frac{-x^2 a^2}{2} + xy - \frac{y^2}{2} \right) dx dy \quad (40)$$

In the further calculations we use the following three well known formulas:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi}, \quad (41)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x e^{-x^2} dx = 0, \quad (42)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx x^2 e^{-x^2} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx e^{-x^2} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}. \quad (43)$$

By making substitutions ($\zeta = y\sqrt{\frac{1-a^2}{2a^2}}$ and $\xi = \frac{x-y}{\sqrt{2}}$), which diagonalize the exponents and

¹We like to note that the final result will be literally valid for any σ_η ; in fact it is independent of σ_η .

by using the complete square technique, for the I_1 we get the following expression:

$$I_1 = -\frac{1}{2} \ln(1 - a^2). \quad (44)$$

Following the same procedure for the second part of the integral we get $I_2 = 0$. Thus the final expression for the mutual information is

$$I(X, Y) = -\frac{1}{2} \ln(1 - a^2). \quad (45)$$

2.10 Numerical example for mutual information analysis

In this subsection we demonstrate an example for the numerical analysis of mutual information, using the above discussed statistical tools, by considering the autoregressive and linear time series.

In statistics, autoregressive models AR(p) describe time series, in which the output variable depends linearly on its own previous values (back up to p time steps). Together with the moving average (MA) model it describes more general types of time series, called ARMA and ARIMA. The Autoregressive model of order p is given by the following formula:

$$X_t = c + \sum_{i=1}^p a_i X_{t-i} + \epsilon_t, \quad (46)$$

where a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p are the parameters of the model and c is a constant. ϵ_t is white noise with zero mean and a constant variance σ^2 .

Let us consider the simplest model, namely AR(1):

$$X_t = c + aX_{t-1} + \epsilon_t. \quad (47)$$

If we consider $|a| < 1$ condition, then the process is stationary. That means the mean of the process remains the same $\mu = E(X_t) = E(X_{t-1})$ hence we get:

$$\mu = \frac{c}{1 - a}.$$

For the numerical analysis we consider the case where $c = 0$ and according to the above equation for this case the mean of the process is zero and the variance is equal to

$$\text{Var}(X_t) = \frac{\sigma_\epsilon^2}{1 - a^2}, \quad (48)$$

where σ_ϵ is the standard deviation of ϵ_t .

As second time series we consider a simple linear model, related to the first time series as follows: $Y_t = aX_{t-1}$.

Figure 1: The plot shows the mutual information analysis for the AR(1) and the linear time series based on the past values of the first time series, by including a Gaussian noise. The variable a is taken from the interval $[0, 1]$, for $a = 1$ the mutual information diverges. The parameters chosen for the algorithms are: $N = 1000$ (length of data set), $K = 5$ and the bin width is equal to 4.93. The figures show that the KNN algorithm coincides better with the analytical curves for the larger a 's, which shows more efficiency of the KNN algorithm.

Finally we estimate the mutual information between them by using both histogram and KNN methods, described in detail above. Since rescaling by any factor a is irrelevant for the mutual information, the computed quantity is the time delayed mutual information of the AR(1) process for time lag 1.

Figure 1 illustrates the result and relationship between mutual information and the a parameter, where a is taken from the interval $[0, 1]$. For $a = 1$ mutual information diverges, where the result qualitatively coincides with the analytical result for the mutual information for the Gaussian case.

The red line in Figure 1 shows the result for the analytical expression of mutual information, namely formula (45), which we derived for the Gaussian distribution. The cyan line illustrates the result by using the KNN algorithm and the blue line shows the mutual information analysis by considering the histogram method. We see there are discrepancies with the analytically obtained curve, which may be caused by approximations of the numerical algorithms.

Finally, two programs, based on histogram and KNN statistical methods for the estimation of mutual information can be found in the Appendix.

Part III

Empirical analysis of financial time series

3 Empirical analysis of financial time series

Understanding the volatile feature of financial markets and their complex behavior intrigues many researchers. As a consequence, different stylized facts and models for investigation of financial time series are devised. Financial time series analysis is a broad field, which includes the theoretical and empirical studies of assets valuation over time.

The focus of this part is on financial volatility, which plays an important role for the risk management and portfolio optimization. More precisely, the risks are measured by the variance of the asset returns and the square root of the variance is volatility. Volatility is simply the degree of variations and fluctuations of a financial time series, i.e. it shows the amount of uncertainty in the change of the price of the asset's value. In particular, volatility is interpreted as the statistical measure of the distribution of returns for a given financial asset per market index.

It is clear that the price range can increase (decrease) impressively over a short time period in both directions. The lower volatility simply indicates the smaller fluctuations in financial assets and in analogy the volatility of an asset is termed to be high, if the prices fluctuate rapidly [107].

The most popular techniques for modeling the volatility are the generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity (GARCH) models invented in [27, 108]. The financial return volatilities can be explained well with aforementioned models and their family.

If the market is hectic, volatilities are large, and usually it will take some time until the market has become calm again. This fact is related to the volatility clustering phenomenon. According to Mandelbrot [109], large changes tend to be followed by large changes, of either sign, and small changes tend to be followed by small changes. The fact of volatility clustering as an aggregation has inspired researchers and has a major impact on the development of stochastic processes in finance. Therefore works are devoted to explain the origin of the volatility clustering in terms of reflection and the behavior of traders, see e.g. [28]. The autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity (ARCH) and the GARCH models are the most common models for describing the clustering phenomenon. These are autoregressive (AR) models, where the variance of the process is a random variable which itself follows an AR process. The observation of volatility clustering gives evidence of predictability of volatility. In other words, there is a memory effect in the size of price change. Moreover, the stronger influence of negative returns than of positive returns on the future volatility and possible predictability have been studied in [110].

In the first part of this chapter, we discuss some asymmetry in financial time series. More precisely, we analyze the correlation between intraday and overnight volatilities by considering different measuring tools. In the second part of the chapter, we discuss the concept of self-

fulfilling prophecy and its influence in financial market, by considering the sentiment and fear index of investors. Let us unveil the above statements by revealing them through technical analysis.

3.1 Asymmetry of cross-correlations between intraday and overnight volatilities

The volatility of equity returns is higher during exchange trading hours than during non-trading hours. It has been shown that the variance of returns from the open-to-close of the trading day is over six time larger than the variance of close-to-open returns over a weekend, e.g. see [111, 112]. The difference between the prices at the opening and closing hours has various reasons, e.g. more public information is clustered during business hours. In particular, it has been shown that the volatility decreases from the opening hour until the early afternoon and rises thereafter. It was also found that the variance of the return is higher for open-to-open than for close-to-close periods [42]. Finally, it has been repeatedly shown that the overnight dynamics is qualitatively different from that during the day [36]-[44]. Various reasons have been proposed for this:

- A foreign equity which is mainly traded on some foreign market (that is open during the night hours of the market studied) reflects mostly its activity in their overnight volatility, and this activity might be very different [43] from the market under consideration.
- The majority of news relevant for fundamental stock price evaluation (company profits, employment rates, general econometric forecasts, wars and natural disasters, ...) are released overnight [113], and there exists a correlation between frequency of news releases and volatilities [44].
- While the market can react during the day to any outside perturbation, it cannot do so during the night, which might also explain the higher volatility immediately after the market opening [36].

Let us use the index k to count trading days (i.e. skipping weekend and other non-trading days), and denote by o_k and c_k the opening and closing prices of one particular equity. Intraday log-returns of this equity are defined as

$$d_k = \ln \frac{c_k}{o_k} , \quad (49)$$

while overnight log-returns are

$$n_k = \ln \frac{o_k}{c_{k-1}} . \quad (50)$$

Thus overnight returns are indexed by the index of the following day. In case of weekends and holidays the over-“night” returns include all changes during the entire non-trading period. Volatilities are in principle defined through the variances of log-returns as observed over an extended time span. But when discussing them on a fine grained temporal scale, they are usually replaced by the absolute values of the log-returns (see e.g. footnote 11 in [38]). We will follow this usage.

Figure 2: Historical time series of stock intraday (panel a) and overnight (panel b) returns for the MDAX index. Data shown refers to all trading days between date and date.

The data we studied consists of 21 individual stocks traded at various stock exchanges (Exxon, Shell, General Electric, Ford, Goldman-Sachs, Bank of America, Citigroup, IBM, Microsoft, Cisco, AIG, BP, Caterpillar and Ford all traded at NYSE; Siemens, Deutsche Bank, Lufthansa, VW and Bayer traded in Frankfurt; and Sony & Mitsubishi traded in Tokyo) and 10 market indices and exchange-traded funds (TecDax, MDax, DAX, Dow Jones, S&P 100, Nasdaq, EuroSTOXX 50, SIM, S&P/ASX and PowerShares QQQ). They were mostly downloaded from Yahoo (<https://finance.yahoo.com/>), the rest from finanzen.net (<http://www.finanzen.net>). The time sequences cover between 10.4 and 45 years, with between 2612 and 13478 data points. Before using them, we cleaned them from some of their artifacts (missing data, wrong data, ...), but not of all. There are many websites that report daily financial data, but for the validation of the data it is useful to check the same dataset from different sources. Despite the availability of cleaning data tools provided by different software producers, we did not use them, first because of their costs and second mostly data cleaning software takes long time. Instead we performed some statistical methods, such as calculation of mean, variance, etc., which can help to check whether there are some anomalous values among them (for example too low minimum or too high maximum values). But for the better understanding of data characteristics we visualized them via graphics and scatter

Figure 3: Data for 31 equities. Each dot corresponds to one equity. The Spearman correlation between intraday volatilities and overnight volatilities during the *subsequent* night are plotted on the x-axis, while the correlations with the *preceding* night are on the y-axis.

plots which could show us for example outliers. Detecting outliers are an important issue, however one should not immediately remove them, because of their significant influence on statistical parameters such as mean and variance. Instead it is essential to figure out why they occur and to understand whether on that date something has happened in the financial world. But in cases where it was obvious that it is simply wrong data we cleaned them.

For instance, we did *not* remove jumps due to stock splitting. After cleaning, they show the typical features well-known from previous analyses, such as fat tails, short-time correlations in the returns, and long-time correlations in the volatilities. For typical examples, see Figure 2. Notice that these data still have outliers (mostly negative, due to crashes, bad annual reports,...). The negative outliers occur mostly for the overnight returns, consistent with the previous observation that negative news are disseminated mostly when the markets are closed. The long autocorrelations of the volatilities are seen both for daytime and overnight.

3.1.1 The observation of asymmetry using Spearman's correlation coefficient

Our main concern is with cross-correlations between intraday and overnight volatilities. Due to the artifacts, irregularities, and strong non-stationarity in the data, we did not use only simple Pearson coefficients. Instead we mostly used Spearman coefficients [114]. Spearman correlation coefficients, as discussed above, show a dependency between two variables, which

Figure 4: Ratios C_{nd}/C_{dn} for the 32 equities and indices shown also in Figure 3. For stocks, the colors indicate the stock exchanges where they are traded.

are based on rank statistics. These are known to be much more robust. It implies monotonic relationships including non-linearity. To a certain extent the Spearman correlation coefficient is insensitive to the difference between raw data. For these reasons it shows more robustness for our finding.

Our main results are shown in Figure 3 and 4. In Figure 3 we show for each equity two cross-correlations between the ranks r_{d_k} and r_{n_k} of the two volatilities $|d_k|$ and $|n_k|$:

$$C_{nd} = \frac{\langle r_{d_k} r_{n_k} \rangle - \langle r_{d_k} \rangle \cdot \langle r_{n_k} \rangle}{\sigma_d \sigma_n}, \quad (51)$$

is the rank correlation between the intraday volatility and the volatility during the *preceding* night (σ_d and σ_n are the square roots of the rank variances), while

$$C_{dn} = \frac{\langle r_{d_k} r_{n_{k+1}} \rangle - \langle r_{d_k} \rangle \cdot \langle r_{n_k} \rangle}{\sigma_d \sigma_n}, \quad (52)$$

gives the analogous correlation with the *following* night. (Note that the averages are taken across all trading days, along with the respective nights). We see that in almost all cases

$$C_{nd} > C_{dn}. \quad (53)$$

Figure 5: Ratios C_{nd}/C_{dn} for the 31 equities and indices are shown by using Pearson correlation coefficient.

For some equities the difference is small, but for others it can be more than a factor of two. In only one case the inequality was violated. Thus the overnight volatility is much stronger correlated with the volatility during the following day than during the preceding day. Otherwise said, overnight volatilities seem to influence strongly what goes on during the following trading day, but do not seem to be strongly influenced by what was going on during the day before.

The ratios C_{nd}/C_{dn} for the equities used in Figure 3 are plotted also in Figure 4, where we have also specified the equities. The first 10 entries in this figure are market indices, while the others correspond to individual stocks. We see no big differences, except that aggregated indices show a somewhat stronger effect. There are also no noticeable differences related to the place where the equity is traded, to the length of the time series, and – in case of individual stocks – to the type of company.

3.1.2 The validity of analyses by using Pearson and mutual information

Next we like to demonstrate that the found asymmetry is not an artifact of the chosen correlation coefficient. It is most clearly seen by use of the Spearman correlation coefficient, but still visible by use of Pearson coefficients, see Figure 5. In comparison to Figure 4,

Figure 6: Ratios I_{nd}/I_{dn} for the 31 equities and indices are shown for mutual information.

however, we observe in Figure 5 a sizable fraction of data points lying below 1.

Alternatives to the Spearman's correlation coefficient are Kendall's τ [115] or mutual information [96], both of which are known to be similarly robust. Let us finally consider here mutual information for proving our results.

As described in the previous section, mutual information is a reduction of uncertainty knowing another random variable and it tells us how much two random variables share information among each other.

Let us recall the equation by considering two random variables X and Y with a joint probability function $p(x, y)$ and marginal probability functions $p(x)$ and $p(y)$:

$$I(X, Y) = \sum_x \sum_y p(x, y) \log \frac{p(x, y)}{p(x)p(y)} \quad (54)$$

where in our case X and Y are the intraday and overnight volatilities. The results are shown in Figure 6, which shows the robustness of our finding. I_{nd} is the mutual information for $(x_k, y_k) = (d_k, n_k)$ and I_{dn} is the mutual information for $(x_k, y_k) = (d_k, n_{k+1})$. Note that in this analysis we use again the absolute values of returns.

For mutual information estimation we use two approaches, histogram and K -nearest neighbor statistics. As discussed in the previous section, while the histogram is easy to comprehend, it has several disadvantages: it depends on the bin width and different initial choices can

change the outcome. In contrast to this conventional method based on binning, the K -nearest neighbor statistics are based on entropy estimation of K -nearest neighbor distances. This means that they are data efficient, adaptive and have minimal bias [101].

Moreover, in the present thesis investigations by taking into account foreign markets in different time zones are also considered. Our analyses show that European markets at their opening time are largely driven by Asian and American markets. On the other side we see that American markets are largely driven by both European and Asian market on the same day, whereas the analyses show stronger correlation between American and Asian markets for the closing prices. There is also evidence that the Asian market is affected by American markets on the previous day.

Another interesting question is about the relation between stocks, conditioned on a third one. Motivated by such analyses, the Pearson partial correlation coefficient has been also performed in [116] and also conditional mutual information can answer such questions.

While the intraday price dynamics is largely influenced by “chartist” behavior, the overnight dynamics is mostly influenced by facts exogenous to the stock market (or at least not directly related to the day-to-day price evolution of the considered equity) and thus of “fundamentalist” nature. What our results suggest is that “fundamentalist” information is more useful in prediction than “chartist” information.

The present analysis cannot of course specify which of the possible external influences (foreign stock markets, company performance reports, news about general economic indicators such as employment rates and forecasted economic growth, wars, economic crises, natural disasters, ...) is of greatest importance for the overnight dynamics, but such information could possibly be obtained by performing a larger study similar to the present one in which equities are grouped according to business sectors, stock exchanges, trading volume, bull *versus* bear markets, etc. Another improvement suggested by our analysis could consist in replacing the simple cross correlations by partial correlations or by transfer entropies [117], testing in this way for linear or non-linear Granger causality [118]. It would be of interest to see whether the asymmetry found in the present thesis is also present at larger time scales, by comparing day/night to night/day results between more distant nights and days. The very fact that different regions in the phase space of a recurrent system can have different powers of predictability has been known for long time [119].

Finally, with the hindsight gained from this analysis, we might also turn to signed returns (in contrast to volatilities) and test whether some parts of a full 24 hours day have more influence on periods than others.

3.2 Self-fulfilling prophecy in finance

The motivation of this part stems from the desire, whether it is possible to make some forecast of an asset price change by using the sentiment and fear index of investors and traders. In general, the inspiration of such analyses has come from a concept called self-fulfilling prophecy, whence because of its nice and important notion, let us comment on in detail.

Self-fulfilling prophecy is a well known concept, which claims that social beliefs and expectations often influence social reality [120]-[123], i.e. the concept describes a connection between beliefs and their outcomes in the situation under consideration. In the literature, the term self-fulfilling prophecy is associated with two sociologists W. I. Thomas and Robert K. Merton. Merton described the idea as a cultural belief that becomes true because people believe that this is true already, i.e. it can take the form of a genuine prediction. The basic idea behind this concept was posited by Thomas, in the literature well known as the Thomas theorem [124]. According to the Thomas theorem: “If men define situations as real, they are real in their consequences”. After all, Merton popularized the concept of self-fulfilling prophecy in his work and defined as follows: “The self-fulfilling prophecy is, in the beginning, a false definition of the situation evoking a new behavior, which makes the originally false conception come true”. In conclusion, the idea points out a general and in some way a crucial key about the social construction of reality, based on prediction.

The famous example of such a phenomenon is a run on a bank, which was postulated by Robert Merton. The hypothesis describes how false rumors could lead to the financial bankruptcy and collapse of the bank, despite its financial solvency, i.e. in spite of the comparative liquidity of the bank’s assets, a false rumor of insolvency affected the actual outcome and brought the insolvency of the bank.

The concept has been used and tested in many fields such as sociology, psychology, education [125, 126], economy [127] and medicine. For example in the latter one, the self-fulfilling prophecy occurs as a placebo effect [128]-[130], which in turn, is medically ineffectual treatment.

In order to gain a better understanding of the attitude and the goal involved in self-fulfilling prophecy, psychologists have tried to improve the dynamics of the process, considering the constraints and the conditions, under which the expectation leads to its own fulfillment. In general, one should mention that self-fulfilling prophecy is not just wishing or expecting something and it will lead to its fulfillment. Otherwise said, wishing alone does not make the expectation to become real: It is a dynamical process, which consists of a series of steps and these steps are crucial to the triggering of a whole idea. The steps simply depend on the underlying phenomenon. Obviously the concept begins with the step of having a wish or an expectation and it ends with the step of the fulfillment of the expectation.

The self-defeating prophecy is the logical converse and complementary the opposite of the self-fulfilling prophecy concept: it is a prediction that prevents what it predicts from happening [131]. As the opposite of the self-fulfilling prophecy, the idea can be taken by referring to any situation that provokes an opposite behavior to the initial expectations. It is again a dynamical process composed of series of steps, which act and begin to operate in such a way, that the expectations will not become true.

There is another interesting concept called self-fulfilling crisis, which refers to a situation that argues the financial crisis is not directly related to the bad economic conditions, but it is a consequence of pessimistic expectations of traders [132, 133].

Let us now tie the concept to specific financial data in order to explore its strength and to make it more intelligible.

3.2.1 Sentiment Index

In the past decades, sentiment, fear or in general opinion mining analyses in the financial sector have become a burning issue [134, 135]. The most important purposes of such analyses is the predictability of possible trends in the stock market prices. These predictions are driven by analyzing the opinions, feelings and emotions of investors and therefore are called sentiment and fear analyses. The latter one is known as a VIX index and we will discuss it in detail in the next section.

Many researchers have been attracted to experiment with such tests, because often financial markets react and move due to the human emotions. In particular, we investigated the analysis of Euwax Sentiment, reported on Boerse Stuttgart website [47]. Euwax Sentiment is a private investor index based on the products of DAX, XDAX and DAX/XDAX combinations. Positive values indicate expectation that the market prices are rising and in analogy negative values indicate expectations of the falling of the prices.

The Euwax Sentiment index is based on the orders which are submitted and executed within 60 seconds. The data consists of real trading transactions, providing traders with high accuracy of frequency, which presents an up to date picture of the market change and evaluation. It is well known that one of the major facts for forecasting the daily volatility of stock market prices is the observation of high frequency data analyses [136]-[138]. Thus the sentiment and fear index could be one of the useful signals for prediction purposes.

The sentiment score is given according to the following formula:

$$\frac{\text{Number of calls} - \text{Number of puts}}{\text{Number of calls} + \text{Number of puts}} \cdot 100, \quad (55)$$

where the scale of values is ranged between [-100, 100]. Long term product investments and purchases and short term product sales create a positive sentiment index, whereas short

product purchases and long products sales indicate a negative sentiment. Due to the division by the overall number of orders, the index value does not depend on the absolute number of the executed orders per day.

Let us briefly review (especially for physicists) what in general option pricing and the above “call” and “put” words in finance mean. An option is a contract, that gives the option holders the right (but not the obligation) to execute a particular transaction (buy or sell) with the option (contract) writer, by following some terms. Calls and puts are two main types of options. More precisely, an option that transfers the right to the owner to buy at a specific price is referred to as a call; Vice versa, an option that gives the right to the owners to sell at a specific price is referred to as a put.

Investors buy puts, in case where they think the price of an asset will fall and sell if they think it will rise. If the market experiences a downward turn this is a worst case scenario for put sellers and vice versa, the maximum profit is gained when the price of the asset is above or at the option’s strike price at the expiration time. In contrast to put option, investors buy calls when they think the price of the particular asset will rise and sell a call, if they think the price will fall. If the stock will not be purchased at the specified price before the expiration date, then the stock loses its value.

The value of an option is determined by various quantities such as the current stock price, the intrinsic value (current stock price – strike price (call option), or strike price – current stock price (put option)), time to expiration and the volatility. The well-known Black-Scholes model is the most widespread option pricing model, which as an input uses these parameters, by giving as an output the market value of the option.

While the price of a stock is rising, more likely the price of a call option will rise and the price of a put option will fall. If the stock price has a downward scenario, then one most likely observes the reverse situation of the call and put options.

We analyzed the correlated structure of DAX and the sentiment index related to it by using different measurement tools such as mutual information. For the analysis we used the intra-day chart presented on the Boerse Stuttgart website, which reports every minute from 9:05 to 20:00 based on the executed orders of the last thirty minutes.

3.2.2 CBOE’s volatility Index (VIX)

Let us in analogy focus on the fear index analysis, by illustrating some figures, which show the usefulness of such analyses and make the above statements visible. Fear or VIX index, is the symbol of the “CBOEs Volatility Index”, which is a measure of the implied volatility of S&P 500, calculated and reported by Chicago Board Options Exchange (CBOE) [48]. In a short time the index achieved popularity between traders and became an important benchmark for

Figure 7: The plot shows the time series of VIX and the different crises, with its minimum value 9.3, maximum value 80.8 and mean 19.6.

the U.S. stock market. VIX continues to be used widespread by traders, in risk management, forecasting and different financial sectors.

The current VIX index demonstrates an expectation of stock market volatility in the near future. More precisely, it indicates the expectation of the implied stock market volatility for S&P 500 index over the next 30 days.

VIX is based on stock options rather than stock prices, so it is built on the call and put options. In general the idea of creating a volatility index from option prices dates back to 1973, after the idea of exchange-traded options emerged. In the further course of such analysis, CBOE was inspired by these ideas and extended the concept of the early efforts. In the literature the VIX term is associated with CBOE's consultant Robert Whaley, who in 1992 developed the volatility instrument based on option prices, which is quoted in percentage points [139].

The VIX was the first effective attempt at tracking the volatility index. As it was launched, the index was an indicator of the implied volatility of S&P 100. Later in 2004 it was developed based on put and call options of a broader index S&P 500. There exists more than 20 years VIX historical prices, so scientific papers related to VIX, dates back since the end of the 80-s. Figure 7 shows the VIX index fluctuations since 1988 until present. Here we see for example that the VIX peaked at the end of August 1998, at 42-44 percent, which coincides with the LTCM downturn. The chart illustrates that before the global crash of 2008, the VIX peaked

Figure 8: Time series of S&P 500 index (panel a) and returns of S&P 500 (panel b), which are obtained by $r_t = \frac{p_{t+1} - p_t}{p_t}$, where $p_{t+1} - p_t$ indicates a price change.

above 30 percent in August 2007 and after two months we see the stock market poked. It followed then with the 2008 global financial crisis and Lehman Brothers bankruptcy. In the figure one can see how the different crises such as the Asian financial crises 97, Early 1990s recession, WorldCom bankruptcy, European Sovereign Debt Crisis gave rise to the anxiety of investors.

Values of VIX above 30 are considered to be large and result from investors' anxiety and uncertainty, whereas values below 20 are usually associated with less hectic and calm market expectations. The higher VIX demonstrates that investors anticipate the huge moves in either direction.

3.2.3 Calculation of the historical volatility and VIX

In this subsection we discuss how we obtained the historical or realized volatility (we call it simply volatility) of S&P 500 and the values of VIX index.

In general volatility describes how much the asset prices are far from their mean values and is measured as the standard deviation of logarithmic returns.

In Figure 8 (panel a) one can see the evaluation of the time series of S&P 500, where time sequences cover 30 years, involving about 8000 data points. The data was mostly downloaded from Yahoo's website. Fortunately, unlike the case of the last chapter on equity data, here we have not seen wrong data and errors, which made the analysis easier.

Most financial analyses study returns instead of prices of stocks, because first they have more interesting statistical properties and second the return of an asset has a scale-free summary of the investment opportunity [140, 141]. Finally, as discussed above, the returns are the

descriptor of the risk measurement and volatility. Panel b in Figure 8 illustrates the returns of S&P 500, which are obtained by the following formula: $r_t = \frac{p_{t+1} - p_t}{p_t}$, where $p_{t+1} - p_t$ indicates a price change.

Not being confused with different names for volatilities, first of all we like to mention the difference between implied and historical volatility: The implied volatility of an option contract is the expected value of the volatility, which will return the value equal to the current market price of the option, i.e its input in option pricing models such as Black-Scholes demonstrates a theoretical value identical to the present market price of the option. As its definition and the name says, implied volatility is a forward looking measure, which differs from historical volatility, which in turn measures historic and past returns of an asset.

For the calculation of the volatility one uses the historical standard deviation, and for the annualized one we have

$$\text{Volatility} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (r_i - \bar{r})^2}{n - 1}} \cdot \sqrt{252} \cdot 100, \quad (56)$$

where the index i is a counter representing each trading day and n the number of trading days in the underlying time frame. The value of r represents compounded daily returns and \bar{r} is the mean of returns over the time window of these n days. Obviously for obtaining a historical volatility chart one can take different values of n . The constant value of 252 represents the annualization factor, i.e. the number of trading days in the U.S. The exact number of trading days on each year might be slightly differs, however for simplicity in the literature this number is taken, for having a constant (approximate) value in the formula. Finally by multiplying with 100 we turn to a percentage scale, by quoting the values as an percentage.

As mentioned above, VIX is constructed for a constant 30-calender day horizon and thus represents the expectation of stock market volatility during the following month. Therefore for the study of the relationship between S&P 500 volatility and VIX in Eq. (56) we consider $n = 21$ trading days.

Let us now discuss briefly about the VIX index calculation. The construction of VIX basically follows from the Black-Scholes theoretical framework. More specifically, The estimation of the future volatility for the asset underlying the option contract is derived from the Black-Scholes formula, where the model assumes the price of the underlying assets follows a geometric Brownian motion with constant drift and volatility.

Although VIX tracks the S&P 500 volatility, the VIX index is being made of options rather than stocks and like the sentiment index, the VIX index calculation is based on calls and puts. It includes the combination of multiple options and derives a cumulative value of volatility. Each option reflects market's expectation of future volatility and VIX indicates how volatile

Figure 9: The comparison of VIX (blue) and S&P 500 (red). The plot illustrates there are periods, with the VIX's price tending to increase despite the market is going down.

are the options until their expiration date. The formula for VIX index calculation includes different parameters such as risk free interest rate, strike prices and the intervals between them and it is constructed by the variance of a near and a next-term options.

Let us briefly recall the VIX formula from the CBOE website:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{2}{T} \sum_i \frac{\Delta K_i}{K_i^2} e^{RT} Q(K_i) - \frac{1}{T} \left(\frac{F}{K_0} - 1 \right)^2, \quad \text{where} \quad \text{VIX} = \sigma \cdot 100.$$

In the above formula we have the following parameters as input: T : time to expiration, F : forward index level desired from index option prices, K_0 : first strike below the forward index level F , K_i : strike price of the i th out-of-the-money option, ΔK_i : interval between strike options, R : risk-free interest rate to expiration and $Q(K_i)$ is the midpoint of the bid-ask spread for each option with strike K_i . (For more information about the parameters we refer to the “White Paper” [139] presented by the CBOE website.)

We downloaded VIX historical data from Yahoo’s website since 1988 to present and for consistency compared with the data downloaded from CBOE website.

Furthermore, CBOE has established other “fear gauge” indices for different stocks as well, for example VXN tracks the NASDAQ 100 and VXD tracks the Dow Jones Industrial average. Similar to its better-known counterpart VIX, the higher the VXN index, the greater expecta-

Comparison of S&P500 volatility and VIX

Figure 10: The plot shows the comparison of VIX and the volatility of S&P 500. It illustrates that VIX can be a good factor for predicting the volatility of S&P 500 index, by analyzing short time scales.

tion for Nasdaq-100 volatility. The function of the index is the same as VIX, this time being constrained as the indicator of market nervousness about the technology sector. Its highest level was observed in October 2008, in the global financial crises, by reaching 86.52% (like VIX, it is quoted in percentage terms). The methodology of VXN calculation is identical to that used for the VIX.

3.2.4 The power of self-fulfilling prophecy in VIX

The index demonstrates investors' attitude toward a financial market. It can be interpreted as a market psychology that reveals through the dynamics of the price change and the reaction of the traders to the price movement. Since the index can have an influence on the dynamics of the market and can reflect the investors' expectation, it can act as a signal of the performance of the self-fulfilling prophecy. For example, Figure 9 highlights that there are periods, where the VIX index tends to increase, whereas the market goes down. The figure illustrates that despite the prices are low, the higher fear index leads to the increment of the S&P 500 index itself, which in turn, shows the power of the self-fulfilling prophecy in VIX. Another example could be found in Figure 10, where it shows that on June 2016 the VIX raised by its close value of 20.97. This local peak was due to a global sell-off of U.S.

Figure 11: Scatter plot of volatility vs. VIX.

equities. As a consequence, the investors around the world by feeling uncertainties in the market, made some decisions, to take gains or experienced losses, which in turn, increased the market volatility. The phenomena is the same what R. Merton describes in his “run in a bank” example, which describes the notion of the self-fulfilling prophecy.

The values of VIX largely depend on investors’ emotions and reactions and the relationship between S&P 500 and VIX is a bull and bear cycle.

Another remarkable and still open problem that attracted us, is the following: We used so far the available data of VIX covering the time since 1988 until present. However, there is no available data for VIX before 1988 on financial websites. So it has intrigued us to calculate the VIX index before this date, by using the corresponding parameters and formulas from CBOE website, for which there is a need of respective database. The idea is to understand how much influence VIX has over the stock market. Otherwise said, how would the stock prices fluctuate if there had not been defined a VIX or fear index. This idea is based again on the notion of self-fulfilling prophecy, which will tell us “does the VIX index actually lead to the fear of traders and consequently influence the market?”

Figure 12: The plot shows comparison of volatility autocorrelation and the VIX-volatility correlation. As is visible there are periods, where VIX-volatility correlation is higher than the volatility autocorrelation.

3.2.5 Has the VIX predictive power or not?

Can the VIX predict the market volatility or not? This is the question that intrigues many researchers and investors. In the literature one can find a contradictive debate. Some sources are criticizing its predictive value, e.g. [142], other scientific reports like [143, 144] and recently Bloomberg [145] evaluate the performance of VIX as a forecast of stock market volatility, especially considering the calm periods of the market. While there are different theories about the predictive power, in this part of the thesis we give some comments, being optimistic on its predictive power.

Figure 10 illustrates a historical price chart of VIX and S&P 500. One can clearly see that the VIX index exhibits a strong relationship with the future volatility by illustrating that VIX can be a good factor for predicting the volatility of the S&P 500 index, by considering high frequency data and small time scale. Second by tracking the time series illustrated in the same figure one can see that S&P 500 volatility lags behind VIX, which is already the first evidence that VIX can give an additional information for forecasting of the volatility. Finally because it embeds market expectations, VIX could be a useful gauge for prediction purposes [143].

The inset of the figure shows data for a smaller period enlarged, where we see more clearly that the volatility lags behind the VIX index. We like to mention that some findings here are

not novel, such as the chart of VIX-volatility, but it is interesting to generate it and analyze the phenomenon qualitatively, by giving own comments.

When speaking about the predictability of the VIX it is important to know the time period that the investor is looking for, since VIX could give useful information for short term investments, but not for long term investments.

Bloomberg [145] argues that VIX can be thought of as the market's prediction of volatility, especially by considering low volatility periods. Let us illustrate that by looking at the S&P 500 volatility vs. VIX scatter plot. The cyan colored line in Figure 11 indicates the level of volatility predicted by VIX. The most of the points lie below the cyan line, which indicates that VIX overestimates volatility. One does not experience a shock at low levels of the VIX. The relation between points shows that volatility is not above 20 percent in cases where VIX is under 12 percent. So, in the range of low volatilities dramatic movement is unlikely (factoring out sudden events). The observation of high volatilities first starts when VIX exceeds 20 percent.

In conclusion, VIX is the implied volatility and demonstrates the expectation value of annualized 30-day S&P 500 volatility. So it can react as the market prediction indicator. VIX plays as a warning sign and if we eliminate the hypothesis of sudden events, news, bankruptcies, political turmoil, etc., then dramatic moves and an immediate switch to a period with high volatility, in general are not common and unlikely.

Another interesting finding is shown in Figure 12, which illustrates the comparison of volatility autocorrelation and VIX-volatility correlation. We consider the Pearson's correlation coefficient between the current value of VIX and the expected value of the volatility in the near future as follows:

$$C(\tau) = \frac{\langle \text{VIX}(t) \cdot \text{vol}(t + \tau) \rangle - \langle \text{VIX} \rangle \langle \text{vol} \rangle}{\sigma_{\text{VIX}} \sigma_{\text{vol}}},$$

where τ indicates 21 trading days in a following month, and σ_{VIX} and σ_{vol} are the standard deviations of the VIX and volatility time series. The current VIX is positively correlated with volatility in the future and the correlation function is not symmetric in the time lag.

As shown in the figure, there are periods, where the VIX-volatility correlation is higher than volatility autocorrelation, which is a striking result, showing that the VIX can be a predictor for the volatility of S&P 500 index. In fact, in a region shown in the figure, we observe that the relationship and dependency between VIX and volatility are remarkable than the volatility with itself. Given this, we conclude that the additional information originated from VIX can lead to the forecasting of the future volatility of the S&P 500 index.

Part IV

Model-based analysis of volatility of cumulative production

4 Model-based analysis of production processes

In this chapter we study the stochastic properties of the cumulative production, based on Wright's or experience curves law, which describes the cost-experience-quantity relationship. Behind this fundamental hypothesis stands a large amount of empirical evidence which motivated us to establish a model-based theory for describing the relationship between volatility of production process, which in turn is of major importance to predict the volatility of the cumulative production by passing time.

In the following sections, various quantities in production process and capital stock modeling based on the probability distribution functions of the processes are derived.

More precisely, in the first part, the focus is on normally distributed noise in the production process. By using the steepest descent method we demonstrate a model-based relationship of volatility of the cumulative production and volatility of the production process itself. The result is stunning and potentially powerful and it is tested for various products and technologies. Furthermore, we generalize the concept and present a complete model for the relationship between these quantities, now based on an arbitrary distribution function of noise in the process. In this chapter a recursion relation of integral type is derived that replaces simulations by highly accurate numerical integration. A new solution yields a systematic control over the efforts done before. Higher order moments, such as kurtosis and skewness will be addressed as well. Moreover using the same procedure the relation between capital stock and the investment is explored. Let us begin with the technical explanations of the above statements.

4.1 Experience curve

First of all let us recast what the experience curves present and why they are useful. There exists a large literature starting with Wright's paper [49], in which he argued that when the total aircraft production doubled, the required labor time decreased by 10 to 15 percent. More general, the learning curve effect ² proposes that for each doubling of the total quantity of a particular product, costs decrease by a fixed proportion rate, (costs include marketing, manufacturing, distribution, etc).

The Boston Consulting Group in the 1960 period observed the experience curve effects for various industries and figured out that the production of any good and commodity gives evidence of the experience curve effect [50]. Based on empirical research, for the experience curves the following mathematical framework, which is a power law function, has been validated:

²Different names used in the literature might be confusing, therefore we want to mention that all these names (experience curve, learning curve or simply Wright's Law) express the same effect.

$$P_n = P_1 n^{-b},$$

where P_1 is the cost of the first unit of production and P_n is the cost of the n -th unit of production. The cumulative volume of production is denoted by n and b is called an experience coefficient. This equation states that the costs decrease by a constant factor for every doubling of cumulative production, which creates a linear relationship between the log of the cost and the log of the cumulative production.

Furthermore, there must be a characteristic pattern that causes the experience curve effect, for instance a development of better tools, automatization, training programs [146]-[150], prior experience and the work complexity task [151, 152]. Let us discuss some of them: The employee in the company regardless of position, needs time which is directly associated with the experience gained for learning the task, i.e. by passing time, labors become more adept and agile to the underlying task. The experience of iteration helps them to spend less time and to make less mistakes for performing the same task. This is valid for all employees in the particular firm and not just those who are directly connected with the production process. (Given this, it is clear that an expert and experienced employee should decrease the companies costs over time).

Another reason to mention here is the network effects, which states that the more a specific product will be ubiquitous and widely-used then the more efficient the network and the demand are and as a consequence costs will be reduced per utility.

The notion of experience curve could also describe the effect between business competitors, e.g. who is faster in reducing the costs, which in turn, could describe the complex interactions and network between them. Given this, the hypothesis may not only project the own firms costs, but costs relative to competitors are of major importance, which in turn will give some information about the market strategy. However the production process is a complex system and many factors have contributions on its development, such as input prices, innovation, etc.

The analysis of experience curve also led to the idea (developed by the Boston Consulting group (BCG)) that in the long run, preserving a high price for an item could create self-defeat, i.e. the opposite effect for the strategy can be observed, although in the short run it can be profitable. The reason for this effect stems from the fact that it simply motivates competitors, by triggering to produce the same item with lower price and the quantity of the product will raise in the market. But according to the experience curve effect if the prices would decline as unit costs are reduced, then the item would not attract other competitors and their entrance to the market could be eliminated. This is one of the strategies that support to maintain share holders in the market safely. For supporting this phenomenon, the underpinned idea of BCG's growth share matrix was developed [153].

We like to note, that from the power of experience the firm profits, yet in general producing products should be accompanied by innovation and invention, because the latter items can dramatically change the history of the firm products. For example all the experience of making only black and white television would be worthless for a firm, if innovation provides in this case the color one.

It is also clear if the production of a product is not growing then the rate of cost declines gradually to zero. On the other hand, if competitors have the same relative market shares and almost the same experience for the specific product then their costs tend to remain the same in the market.

The curves of different products have a different slope and downward gradient, which means different source of cost reduction. The reasons for this discrepancy stems from the fact that producing different products demand different time and level of experience, e.g. production of a nuclear reactor and semiconductors demand different time, performance and experience. The slope of the curve can also characterize the efficiency of learning, for example, a steep learning curve represents a quickly-learned task. Contrarily, difficult subjects require a longer duration, which leads to a shallower curve.

In conclusion, the experience curve hypothesis states that costs follow a definite pattern due to the accumulated production experience. Knowing that constant increasing rate is for each year the same, one can figure out what would be the effect on cost in the upcoming year. For example, in [51] it has been found that experience curves can be used to estimate future technology costs, considering the shape of the forecast error distribution. The hypothesis can provide a significant understanding of the market strategy, for instance export potentials due to the knowledge of experience levels, the prediction of future prices, given some information about the market costs decrease by some consistent rate of decline, the applicability in risks management, etc.

4.2 Volatility of production for narrow distributions

It was first discovered by Sahal [55] that the exponentially increasing cumulative production and exponentially decreasing costs gives an experience curve law, which indicates a linear relationship between the log of the cost and the log of the cumulative production.

For not causing confusion let us mention that Wright's law describes cost-experience relationship, which is a power law. But experience itself grows exponentially, because we assumed that production grows exponentially, as a geometric random walk with drift. The exponential growth of production and thus experience gained from this comes from the observation which was found first in [55]. Further investigations followed by, e.g. [154, 155]. (Regarding the exponential growth of the production and experience the curious reader is deferred to figures

2 and 3 in [51]. Note that the constant growth rate leads to a perfectly exponential growth (deterministic as in [55]).

As discussed above, in our model we consider that empirically cumulative production growth follows a smooth exponential behavior in the presence of noise, by assuming that production is a geometric random walk with drift g and variance σ_a^2 . Within this model, cumulative production Z_t is given by:

$$Z_t = \sum_{j=0}^t e^{gj} e^{a_1} \dots e^{a_j}, \quad (57)$$

where a_1, a_2, \dots are stochastic i.i.d. variables, which describe the noise in the production process.

Let us first consider the special case, where a_1, a_2, \dots are normally distributed i.i.d. variables, with mean zero and variance σ_a^2 . As mentioned before, for the calculation of cumulative production and its volatility for the narrow distribution the saddle point method is used. The main idea of the saddle point is to approximate an integral by taking into account only the range of the integration where the integrand takes its maximum. A priori, this can only be correct for small variance σ_a^2 .

Next we give here short summary of the results and the calculation are deferred to the next section.

First we calculate the expectation value of cumulative production and its variance, which lead to the multiple integral over a_i

$$\begin{aligned} E(\log Z) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \log Z \prod_{i=1}^t \frac{da_i}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_a^2}} \exp \left[-\frac{a_i^2}{2\sigma_a^2} \right] \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \prod_{i=1}^t \frac{da_i}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_a^2}} e^{S(\{a_i\})}, \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

with $S(\{a_i\}) = \log(\log Z) - \sum_{i=1}^t \frac{a_i^2}{2\sigma_a^2}$.

We would like to note that $\log Z$ is a function of random i.i.d. variables which have Gaussian distributions (with variance σ_a^2). Our independent variables are $a_i, i = 1 \dots n$ and $Z(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ is a function of them. Therefore one should integrate over independent a_i 's. Eq. (58) expresses this statement, namely, we have a product over identical Gaussian distributions for each variable a_i .

The applicability of our method essentially depends whether σ_a is small enough. The final justification comes from comparison with empirical data, which agree with our result with reasonable accuracy.

The essence of the saddle point method is to approximate the integral by taking into account only that portion of the range of the integration where the integrand assumes large values.

Figure 13: The plot shows the comparison of the volatility of cumulative production σ_x and the volatility of the production σ_a by empirically and analytically obtained results. The plot is taken from our paper [51]. Asterisks demonstrate chemicals, red squares hardware, green dots consumer goods, triangles energy and light blue dots demonstrate food.

More specifically, in our calculation, we find the maxima of the integrands and approximate fluctuations around these points keeping quadratic and neglecting higher order terms.

For $\sigma_a^2 \ll 1$ the saddle point method yields explicit results, for instance the variance of $\log Z(t)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}(\log Z(t)) &= E(\log^2 Z) - E(\log Z)^2 \\ &= \sigma_a^2 \left(\frac{2e^g + 1}{1 - e^{2g}} + t \right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

Finally, the main result of this method is *volatility*, i.e. the variance of *volatility variable* $\Delta \log Z := \log Z_t - \log Z_{t-1}$ for large time $t \rightarrow \infty$ and is given by the following expression (valid for $g > 0$ and small σ_a^2):

$$\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) \equiv \sigma_x^2 = \sigma_a^2 \tanh\left(\frac{g}{2}\right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (60)$$

The result for the limit $g \rightarrow \infty$ is intuitively clear: $\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z)$ has to be identical to $\text{Var}(g + a_t)$, which is equal to σ_a^2 . In the other extreme, namely $g = 0$, the variable Z_t does not grow exponentially with t . As Z_t fluctuates weakly around the value t , we may intuitively understand in this case $\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) = 0$. Furthermore, since $\tanh\left(\frac{g}{2}\right) < 1$ we have

always $\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) < \sigma_a^2$ an inequality, which means the volatility of cumulative production is lower than the volatility of production. This is not surprising, because the integration and accumulation act as a low pass filter, which in our case makes cumulative production smoother than the production itself. This finding is also visible in empirical data of volatility of production compared to the volatility of the cumulative production. For the details we refer to Table 1 in [51]. Note that in realistic production processes, there are correlations induced, e.g. by seasonal effects.

We have tested this remarkably simple, but potentially powerful relationship using empirically available data. Figure 13 shows the test of this finding, which illustrates that the volatility generated by empirical data and the theoretical analysis based on Eq. (60) coincides pretty well. This is the first time that a relationship between these two has been derived.

For testing the formula one needs the values σ_x , σ_a and g for each single dataset. The data used here was created at the Santa Fe Institute and it can be accessed at pcdb.santafe.edu. The data is created from experience curves existing in the literature and for the below listed technologies it is collected in Table 1 in our paper [51]:

The emphasis was on 51 technologies including different sectors (chemical, energy, hardware, food, etc.), where chemicals demonstrate a dominant part of the database. More specifically, the data studied here consists of the following products and technologies: Automotive, Milk, Neoprene Rubber, Phthalic Anhydride, Sodium, Pentaerythritol, Methanol, Hard Disk Drive, Geothermal Electricity, Phenol, Transistor, Formaldehyde, Ethanolamine, Caprolactam, Ammonia, Acrylic Fiber, Ethylene Glycol, DRAM, Benzene, Aniline, VinylAcetate, Vinyl Chloride, Polyethylene LD, Acrylonitrile, Styrene, Maleic Anhydride, Ethylene, Urea, Polyester Fiber, Bisphenol A, Paraxylene, Polyvinylchloride, Low Density Polyethylene, Sodium Chlorate, TitaniumSponge, Photovoltaics, Monochrome Television, Cyclohexane, Polyethylene HD, Laser Diode, Aluminum, Beer, Primary Aluminum, Polystyrene, Primary Magnesium and Wind Turbine.

4.2.1 Analytical treatment by the saddle point method

First let us derive Eq. (60) in detail. In order to obtain this, we propose here a useful and powerful method, which is based on the saddle point approximation, described in the second chapter.

First of all we compute the expectation value of $z = \log Z$, where

$$Z_t = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^t e^{y_i},$$

and

$$y_i = g \cdot i + a_1 + \cdots + a_i.$$

For simplicity, in the further calculations we omit to write the index t for Z , since the derivation part is focused on the a^* saddle point for a fixed t .

Assuming that a_1, \dots, a_t are i.i.d. with distributions

$$P(a_i = a) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_a^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{a^2}{2\sigma_a^2}\right).$$

This leads to the (multiple) integral (the range of integration variables a_i are $(-\infty, \infty)$)

$$E(\log Z) = \int \log Z \prod_{i=1}^t \frac{da_i}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_a^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{a_i^2}{2\sigma_a^2}\right).$$

It is unlikely that this integral can be computed exactly. We will apply saddle point method which assumes that $\sigma_a^2 \ll 1$.

The saddle point is defined from the system of equations ($n = 1, 2, \dots, t$ and $\partial_n \equiv \partial/\partial a_n$)

$$\partial_n \left(\log(\log Z) - \frac{a_n^2}{2\sigma_a^2} \right) = 0,$$

or

$$\frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z} - \frac{a_n}{\sigma_a^2} = 0,$$

which we rewrite as

$$a_n = \sigma_a^2 \frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z}.$$

Since we are going to make calculations up to order σ_a^2 , it is legitimate to substitute $a_i = 0$.

Thus for the saddle point (a_1^*, \dots, a_t^*) we get

$$a_n^* = \sigma_a^2 \frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z} \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4).$$

Expanding up to order σ_a^2 for the $\log Z|_{a_i=a_i^*}$ we get

$$\log Z|_{a_i=a_i^*} = \left(\log Z + \sigma_a^2 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \right) \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (61)$$

The contribution of the Gaussian term is

$$\exp\left(-\sum_{i=1}^t \frac{a_i^2}{2\sigma_a^2}\right) \Big|_{a_i=a_i^*} = 1 - \frac{\sigma_a^2 \sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2}{2 Z^2 \log^2 Z} \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (62)$$

Below we should calculate the matrix of quadratic fluctuations. For second derivatives we get

$$\partial_n \partial_m \log \log Z = \frac{\partial_n \partial_m Z}{Z \log Z} - \frac{\partial_n Z \partial_m Z (1 + \log Z)}{Z^2 \log^2 Z}.$$

Incorporating this (with factor 1/2 coming from the Taylor's formula for the second order coefficient) with the initial Gaussian term, for the matrix of quadratic form we get

$$G_{n,m} = \frac{1}{2\sigma_a^2} \left(\delta_{n,m} + \sigma_a^2 \left(-\frac{\partial_n \partial_m Z}{Z \log Z} + \frac{(1 + \log Z) \partial_n Z \partial_m Z}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \right) \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4) \right).$$

Recall now the Gauss formula for the integral

$$\int \exp \left(- \sum_{n,m=1}^t \xi_n G_{n,m} \xi_m \right) \prod_{i=1}^t d\xi_i = (\det G)^{-1/2} \pi^{t/2}.$$

Using

$$\det G = \exp(\text{tr} \log G).$$

Up to desired order we get

$$\begin{aligned} (2\sigma_a^2)^{-t/2} (\det G)^{-1/2} &= \\ &= 1 + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^t \partial_i^2 Z}{Z \log Z} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2 (1 + \log Z)}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \right) \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

Multiplying all factors given by Eqs. (61), (62), (63) we finally get

$$E(\log Z) = \log Z + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \sum_{i=1}^t \left(\frac{\partial_i^2 Z}{Z} - \frac{(\partial_i Z)^2}{Z^2} \right) \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4).$$

Notice that

$$Z|_{a_i=0} := Z_0(t) = \sum_{i=0}^t e^{ig} = \frac{1 - e^{g(t+1)}}{1 - e^g} \quad (64)$$

$$\partial_i Z|_{a_i=0} = \partial_i^2 Z|_{a_i=0} = Z_0(t) - Z_0(i-1), \quad (65)$$

so that we can rewrite above expression as

$$\begin{aligned} E(\log Z(t)) &= \log Z_0(t) + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \sum_{i=1}^t \left(\frac{Z_0(t) - Z_0(i-1)}{Z_0(t)} - \frac{(Z_0(t) - Z_0(i-1))^2}{Z_0(t)^2} \right) \\ &\quad + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

If $g > 0$ in the large t limit one gets

$$E(\log Z(t))|_{t \rightarrow \infty} = g(t+1) - \log(e^g - 1) + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{4 \sinh(g)} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (67)$$

Now let us calculate the expectation value $E(\log^2 Z)$.

The integral we have to compute is

$$\int \log^2 Z \prod_{i=1}^t \frac{da_i}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_a^2}} \exp -\frac{a_i^2}{2\sigma_a^2}.$$

The saddle point equations

$$\partial_n \left(2 \log(\log Z) - \frac{a_n^2}{2\sigma_a^2} \right) = 0,$$

or

$$2 \frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z} - \frac{a_n}{\sigma_a^2} = 0,$$

which gives

$$a_n = 2\sigma_a^2 \frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z}.$$

As in the previous case on the right hand side we can substitute $a_i = 0$ and for the saddle point (a_1^*, \dots, a_t^*) we get

$$a_n^* = 2\sigma_a^2 \frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z} \Big|_{a_n=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4).$$

Up to order σ_a^2 expansion for $\log^2 Z$ we get

$$\log^2 Z|_{a_i=a_i^*} = \log^2 Z + 4\sigma_a^2 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2}{Z^2} \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (68)$$

The contribution of the Gaussian term is

$$\exp \left(-\frac{a_i^2}{2\sigma_a^2} \right) \Big|_{a_i=a_i^*} = 1 - 2\sigma_a^2 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (69)$$

The matrix of quadratic fluctuations is

$$G_{n,m} = \frac{1}{2\sigma_a^2} \left(\delta_{n,m} + 2\sigma_a^2 \left(-\frac{\partial_n \partial_m Z}{Z \log Z} + \frac{(1 + \log Z) \partial_n Z \partial_m Z}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \right) \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4) \right).$$

Up to desired order we get

$$\begin{aligned} & (2\sigma_a^2)^{-t/2}(\det G)^{-1/2} = \\ & = 1 + \sigma_a^2 \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^t \partial_i^2 Z}{Z \log Z} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2 (1 + \log Z)}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \right) \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (70)$$

Multiplying all factors we finally get

$$\begin{aligned} E(\log^2 Z) &= \log^2 Z + \\ &+ \sigma_a^2 \sum_{i=1}^t \left(\frac{(\partial_i Z)^2}{Z^2} + \left(\frac{\partial_i^2 Z}{Z} - \frac{(\partial_i Z)^2}{Z^2} \right) \log Z \right) \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

For the variance we get

$$E(\log^2 Z) - (E(\log Z))^2 = \sigma_a^2 \sum_{i=1}^t \frac{(\partial_i Z)^2}{Z^2} \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (72)$$

or

$$\text{Var}(\log^2 Z(t)) = \sigma_a^2 \sum_{i=1}^t \frac{(Z_0(t) - Z_0(i-1))^2}{Z_0(t)^2} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (73)$$

If $g > 0$ and $t \rightarrow \infty$ we get

$$\text{Var}(\log^2 Z(t)) = \sigma_a^2 \left(\frac{2e^g + 1}{1 - e^{2g}} + t \right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (74)$$

In a similar way we compute the quantity

$$\begin{aligned} & E(\log Z(t) \log Z(t+1)) - E(\log Z(t))E(\log Z(t+1)) \\ &= \sigma_a^2 \sum_{i=1}^{t+1} \frac{\partial_i Z(t) \partial_i Z(t+1)}{Z(t)Z(t+1)} \Big|_{a_i=0} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4) = \\ &= \sigma_a^2 \sum_{i=1}^t \frac{(Z_0(t) - Z_0(i-1))(Z_0(t+1) - Z_0(i-1))}{Z_0(t)Z_0(t+1)} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

For $g > 0$ and large t the result is

$$\begin{aligned} & E(\log Z(t) \log Z(t+1)) - E(\log Z(t))E(\log Z(t+1)) \\ &= \sigma_a^2 \left(\frac{e^g + 2}{1 - e^{2g}} + t \right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (76)$$

Incorporating (74), (76) for the variance of $\Delta \log Z$ we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) &= E((\log Z(t+1) - \log Z(t))^2) - (E(\log Z(t+1) - \log Z(t)))^2 \\
&= \text{Var}(\log Z(t+1)) + \text{Var}(\log Z(t)) \\
&\quad - 2(E(\log Z(t) \log Z(t+1)) - E(\log Z(t))E(\log Z(t+1))) \\
&= \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{t+1} \left(\frac{Z_0(t) - Z_0(i-1)}{Z_0(t)} - \frac{Z_0(t+1) - Z_0(i-1)}{Z_0(t+1)} \right)^2 + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4) = \\
&= \frac{\sigma_a^2 (e^{g(t+1)} - e^{g(t+2)})^2 (2e^g - 2e^{g(t+2)} + e^{2g(t+2)} - 2e^{g(t+3)} + e^{2g(t+2)} - t - 1)}{(e^{2g} - 1)(e^{g(t+1)} - 1)^2 (e^{g(t+2)} - 1)^2}.
\end{aligned} \tag{77}$$

The final result for $g > 0$ in large t limit is

$$\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) \equiv \sigma_x^2 = \sigma_a^2 \tanh\left(\frac{g}{2}\right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \tag{78}$$

Since

$$\tanh\left(\frac{g}{2}\right) < 1,$$

always

$$\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) < \sigma_a^2.$$

In this model-based result we observe the dependence of the volatility on the drift of the process. The finding will allow us to predict the volatility of the cumulative production, by knowing the drift and volatility of the experience or production itself. The method and the solution can shed light also on other important areas, for instance later we will use the finding for the derivation of capital from the net capital and the investment.

Note the implication only holds in the limit $\sigma_a^2 \rightarrow 0$, otherwise there are correction terms $\mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4)$. Therefore in the next section we will consider the general case which is valid for any σ_a and arbitrary distribution.

4.3 Volatility of the production for an arbitrary distribution

The core result of this section is the investigation of the volatility of cumulative production for more general distribution functions of a_t 's than considered above. Let us assume that in Eq. (57), a_1, a_2, \dots are stochastic i.i.d. variables which are distributed according to some distribution function ρ_a of any shape and width.

We are interested in the distribution function of the log of cumulative production $z_t := \log Z_t$ which we call ρ_{z_t} . From this distribution function we can calculate all important characteristic quantities of the system. Surprisingly, the distribution function can be shown to satisfy a useful recursion relation for successive times:

$$\rho_{z_{t+1}}(x) = \frac{1}{1 - \exp(-x)} \cdot \rho_a * \rho_{z_t}(\log(\exp(x) - 1) - g), \quad (79)$$

where $*$ denotes convolution $f * g(x) = \int dy f(x - y) * g(y)$ and the argument of the convolution in (79) is a non-linear function of x with derivative appearing as prefactor. For the comprehensive derivation of Eq. (79) we refer to the next subsection.

Generally Eq. (79) has to be solved numerically by recursions. Numerical analyses can be done to high accuracy and completely replace simulations, which are time consuming and sometimes inaccurate.

It is possible to obtain analytic results at least for two cases. In the case of a distribution of ρ_a with main weight around some x_0 and a value of g such that $g + x_0 > 0$ we find for large t an asymptotic solution. In this case only large values of x matter and (79) linearizes to $\rho_{z_{t+1}}(x) = \rho_a * \rho_{z_t}(x - g)$. The second case is a narrow distribution of ρ_a , which we already discussed in the last section.

Eq. (79) is highly useful in numerical calculations, especially because the convolution integral can be carried out efficiently and the convergence for increasing time is fast. Of course it would be desirable to treat the time evolution of the probability distribution function for arbitrary t fully analytically such as in [79], where the exact probability distribution functions for the Parrondo's games are derived (for the detailed explanation we refer to the chapter five). The analytical solution is the subject of current investigation.

4.3.1 Probability distribution functions of production processes

Let us now derive Eq. (79) in detail. In the first step, the preliminary analysis was done, for getting closer to the main goal and results. To this end, we present here the expectation values of products of Z 's, which lead to the further investigations of the variance of the cumulative production Z_t .

Let us recall

$$Z_t := \sum_{j=0}^t Q_j, \quad (80)$$

where

$$Q_j := e^{gj} e^{a_1} \dots e^{a_j}, \quad (Q_0 = 1) \quad (81)$$

where the drift g is a constant and a_1, a_2, \dots are stochastic i.i.d. variables.

We further define the expectation values

$$\langle e^{a_j} \rangle =: x, \quad \langle e^{2a_j} \rangle =: y. \quad (82)$$

Note that these objects are independent of the index j . Also note that the expectation values of the exponentials of a_j are not the exponentials of the expectation values of a_j .

Now we can easily calculate the expectation value of Q_j and Z_t . We find

$$\langle Q_j \rangle = e^{gj} \langle e^{a_1} \dots e^{a_j} \rangle = e^{gj} \langle e^{a_1} \rangle \dots \langle e^{a_j} \rangle, \quad (83)$$

because the exponentials of the different a_i are independent. Hence

$$\langle Q_j \rangle = e^{gj} x^j = (e^g x)^j, \quad \langle Z_t \rangle = \sum_{j=0}^t (e^g x)^j = \frac{(e^g x)^{t+1} - 1}{(e^g x) - 1}. \quad (84)$$

The calculation of expectation values of products of Z 's like $\langle Z_t Z_s \rangle$ is more complicated:

$$\langle Z_t Z_s \rangle = \sum_{j=0}^t \sum_{i=0}^s \langle Q_j Q_i \rangle. \quad (85)$$

In the product of $Q_j Q_i$ we have factors like e^{a_n} and e^{2a_m} . For $j < i$ we find

$$Q_j Q_i = e^{g(j+i)} e^{a_1} \dots e^{a_j} \cdot e^{a_1} \dots e^{a_i} = e^{g(j+i)} e^{2a_1} \dots e^{2a_j} \cdot e^{a_{j+1}} \dots e^{a_i}. \quad (86)$$

In this case the expectation value is

$$\langle Q_j Q_i \rangle = e^{g(j+i)} \langle e^{2a_1} \dots e^{2a_j} \cdot e^{a_{j+1}} \dots e^{a_i} \rangle = e^{g(j+i)} y^j x^{i-j}. \quad (87)$$

Here we calculate $\langle Z_t Z_s \rangle$ for the case $s = t$ where we regroup the terms in the double sum in diagonal and off-diagonal terms

$$Z_t Z_t = \sum_{j=0}^t \sum_{i=0}^t Q_j Q_i = \sum_{j=0}^t Q_j Q_j + 2 \sum_{j=0}^t \sum_{i=j+1}^t Q_j Q_i. \quad (88)$$

We find

$$\langle Z_t Z_t \rangle = \sum_{j=0}^t \langle Q_j Q_j \rangle + 2 \sum_{j=0}^t \sum_{i=j+1}^t \langle Q_j Q_i \rangle = \sum_{j=0}^t e^{g(2j)} y^j + 2 \sum_{j=0}^t \sum_{i=j+1}^t e^{g(j+i)} y^j x^{i-j}. \quad (89)$$

Doing the sums we find

$$\langle Z_t Z_t \rangle = 2 \frac{(e^g x)^{t+1} (e^g y/x)^{t+1} - 1}{e^g x - 1} \frac{(e^g y/x)^{t+1} - 1}{e^g y/x - 1} - \frac{e^g x + 1}{e^g x - 1} \frac{(e^{2g} y)^{t+1} - 1}{e^{2g} y - 1}. \quad (90)$$

Now the variance can be calculated $\langle Z_t Z_t \rangle - \langle Z_t \rangle^2$. This is one of the approach for calculation the variance of the log Z , but below we will propose a better mechanism for that.

Let us now propose another mechanism for deriving the recursion expression (79). Note that the modified object

$$\tilde{Z}_t := \sum_{j=0}^t e^{g^j} e^{a_2} \dots e^{a_{j+1}} \quad (91)$$

has the same distribution function as Z_t , because we have used different, but independent and identically distributed a_i 's. So $\tilde{z}_t := \log \tilde{Z}_t$ is distributed according to $\rho_{\tilde{z}_t} = \rho_{z_t}$. Note that

$$1 + e^{g+a_1} \tilde{Z}_t = 1 + \sum_{j=0}^t e^{g(j+1)} e^{a_1} e^{a_2} \dots e^{a_{j+1}} = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{t+1} e^{g^i} e^{a_1} e^{a_2} \dots e^{a_i} = Z_{t+1}. \quad (92)$$

Therefore we have

$$z_{t+1} = \log(1 + \exp(g + a_1 + \tilde{z}_t)) = f(g + a_1 + \tilde{z}_t), \quad (93)$$

where we have used the definition of the function f :

$$f(x) := \log(1 + \exp(x)). \quad (94)$$

The stochastic variable $a_1 + \tilde{z}_t$ is distributed according to the convolution of ρ_a with ρ_{z_t} . The distribution of $g + a_1 + \tilde{z}_t$ is the convolution with a subsequent shift of the argument:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{a_1 + \tilde{z}_t} &= \rho_{a_1} * \rho_{\tilde{z}_t} = \rho_a * \rho_{z_t}, \\ \rho_{g + a_1 + \tilde{z}_t}(x) &= \rho_a * \rho_{z_t}(x - g). \end{aligned} \quad (95)$$

With (93) and (95) we can calculate the distribution function $\rho_{z_{t+1}}$ of z_{t+1} . If we use the arguments x for $\rho_{g+a_1+\tilde{z}_t}$ and $y = f(x)$ for $\rho_{z_{t+1}}$ we find

$$\rho_{z_{t+1}}(y) dy = \rho_{g+a_1+\tilde{z}_t}(x) dx, \quad (96)$$

and from this

$$\rho_{z_{t+1}}(y) = [f'(x)]^{-1} \rho_{g+a_1+\bar{z}_t}(x) = [f'(x)]^{-1} \rho_a * \rho_{z_t}(x - g). \quad (97)$$

Now we use $f'(x) = \exp(x)/(1 + \exp(x))$ and $x = f^{-1}(y) = \log(\exp(y) - 1)$ and reach one of our main findings:

$$\rho_{z_{t+1}}(x) = \frac{1}{1 - \exp(-x)} \cdot \rho_a * \rho_{z_t}(\log(\exp(x) - 1) - g). \quad (98)$$

Figure 14: Plot of probability distribution functions of $\log Z_t$ of the Gaussian distributed ρ_a for different time steps, where $g = 0.2$ and $\sigma_a = 1$ are chosen. The inset shows curves on a large time scale.

Figures 14, 15 and 16 show the distributions of cumulative production for different types of noise and several time steps. Note that for Gaussian ρ_a the distribution functions for $\log Z_t$ have positive skewness and the asymptotic growth of the mean is linear in t (see Figs. 14, 15). For Lorentzian ρ_a the distribution for $\log Z_t$ has a peak at zero (see Figure 16). This means that there is a sizable probability for no production for a long time which stems from the fat tail for negative increments of the production which causes resting. In contrast to the Gaussian case the location of the maximum of the distribution function for $\log Z_t$ looks stationary.

Figure 15: Plot of probability distribution functions of $\log Z_t$ of Gaussian distributed noise for different time steps, where $g = 0.2$ and $\sigma_a = 0.1$ are chosen. The inset shows curves on a large time scale.

Figure 16: Plot of probability distribution functions of $\log Z_t$ of Lorentzian distributed noise for different time steps, where $g = 0.2$ and width equal to 1 are chosen. The inset shows curves on a large time scale.

4.4 The distribution of volatility

The quantity of our interest is the volatility, which is by definition the variance of the distribution function $z_t - z_{t-1}$. We observe

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta z_t &:= z_t - z_{t-1} = \log Z_t - \log Z_{t-1} \\ &= -\log \left(1 - \frac{Z_t - Z_{t-1}}{Z_t} \right).\end{aligned}\quad (99)$$

We define:

$$Y_t := \frac{Z_t}{Z_t - Z_{t-1}}. \quad (100)$$

In the next subsection we show Y_t is distributed as Z_t in Eq. (57) with $g \rightarrow -g$ and $a_i \rightarrow -a_i$, see Eq. 101.

From the above expression we get the following result for the distribution function of the variable $y_t = \log Y_t$:

$$\rho_{\Delta z_t}(x) = \frac{1}{\exp(x) - 1} \rho_{y_t}(-\log(1 - \exp(-x))), \quad (101)$$

where ρ_{y_t} satisfies the same recursion as ρ_{z_t} , after changing the signs of g and a_i , as mentioned above.

4.4.1 Derivation of volatility

Let us now derive Eq. (101) in detail:

According to the definition of Y_t we have $Y_t = \frac{Z_t}{Q_t}$, with

$$Z_t := \sum_{j=0}^t Q_j, \quad Q_j := e^{gj} e^{a_1} \dots e^{a_j}, \quad (102)$$

where g is a constant, and a_1, a_2, \dots are stochastic i.i.d. variables which are distributed according to some distribution function ρ_a . Now – luckily – Y_t has the same structure as Z_t if we replace the constant g and the stochastic variables a_i by g and $-a_i$:

$$Y_t := \frac{Z_t}{Q_t} = \sum_{j=0}^t \frac{Q_j}{Q_t}, \quad \frac{Q_j}{Q_t} = e^{g(j-t)} e^{-a_{j+1}} \dots e^{-a_t}. \quad (103)$$

Next we define

$$\tilde{g} := -g, \quad \tilde{a}_1 := -a_t, \quad \tilde{a}_2 := -a_{t-1}, \quad \dots, \tilde{a}_t := -a_1 \quad (104)$$

Figure 17: Plot of probability distribution functions of the volatility variable for the Gaussian case for ρ_a and different time steps, where $g = 0.2$ and $\sigma_a = 1$. The inset is considered for a large time scale.

And indeed

$$\frac{Q_j}{Q_t} = e^{g(j-t)} e^{-a_{j+1}} \dots e^{-a_t} = e^{\tilde{g}(t-j)} e^{\tilde{a}_1} \dots e^{\tilde{a}_{t-j}}. \quad (105)$$

Hence

$$Y_t = \sum_{j=0}^t e^{\tilde{g}(t-j)} e^{\tilde{a}_1} \dots e^{\tilde{a}_{t-j}} = \sum_{j=0}^t e^{\tilde{g}j} e^{\tilde{a}_1} \dots e^{\tilde{a}_j}. \quad (106)$$

As mentioned above we find that the distribution function of $y_t := \log Y_t$ corresponds to that of $z_t := \log Z_t$, by taking into account sign changes of g and a_i . Hence it satisfies the recursion relation derived in the subsection 4.2.1.

$$\rho_{y_{t+1}}(x) = \frac{1}{1 - \exp(-x)} \cdot \rho_{-a} * \rho_{y_t}(\log(\exp(x) - 1) + g). \quad (107)$$

Figures 17 and 18 illustrate volatility distributions $\rho_{\Delta z_t}$, considering for ρ_a normal and Lorentzian distributions. The figures show the different behaviors of $\rho_{z_t}(x)$, with singular (but integrable) characteristics at $x = 0$ for i.e. $g \geq 0$. The first few time steps show sizable changes whereas only small changes happen at larger times.

Figure 18: Plot of probability distribution functions of the volatility variable for the Lorentzian case for ρ_a and different time steps, where $g = 0.2$ and width is equal to 1. The inset shows curves on a large time scale.

4.4.2 Comparison to the saddle point result

In order to demonstrate the usefulness of Eq. (79) and (101) let us derive from it Eq. (60), which is the result of the saddle point approximation.

ρ_a is given by a narrow distribution around 0 and variance σ_a^2 and correspondingly ρ_{y_t} is defined by the mean $\bar{y}_t = \log(\sum_{j=0}^t e^{-jg})$ and σ_t^2 .

Due to the additivity feature of the variance under convolution, the narrow $\rho_a * \rho_{y_t}$ has the variance equal to $\sigma_t^2 + \sigma_a^2$.

Let us use variable transformation in Eq. (101). Then we get ($\sigma_t := \sigma_{y_t}$)

$$\frac{d(\log(e^x - 1) + g)}{dx} \sigma_{t+1} = \sqrt{\sigma_t^2 + \sigma_a^2}, \quad (108)$$

where $x = \bar{y}_t$. For large times $t \rightarrow \infty$ we get

$$\sigma_\infty^2 = \frac{1}{e^{2g} - 1} \sigma_a^2. \quad (109)$$

Let us now calculate the main result, namely $\sigma_{\Delta z_t}$, the volatility for narrow distributions. To this end we need to transform variables in Eq. (79)

$$\sigma_{\Delta z_t} = (e^x - 1) \sigma_t. \quad (110)$$

Figure 19: Plot of the ratio of the numerically exact value of volatility and the saddle point approximation versus various values of the variance σ_a^2 of noise, and fixed drift, $g = 0.1$.

For x equal to its maximum we have

$$-\log(1 - e^{-x}) = \bar{y}_t \quad (111)$$

and for $t \rightarrow \infty$ this amounts to $x = g$.

Finally, we obtain the result for the special, narrow distributed function, which above was obtained by the saddle point approximation

$$\sigma_{\Delta z_t} = \sqrt{\tanh\left(\frac{g}{2}\right)}\sigma_a. \quad (112)$$

We also compared our numerical results for general values of σ_a^2 with the saddle point result obtained in Eq. (60). These analyses show that the general treatment of the probability distributions and the saddle point approximation coincide for small variance σ_a^2 .

Figure 19 shows that for small values of σ_a the analytical approximation and the numerical results coincide whereas for larger σ_a we see sizable deviations. The volatility for intermediate (large) values of σ_a takes larger (smaller) values than the result of the saddle point approximation.

4.5 Volatility of the process without memory in the noise

Here we discuss about a model, which does not possess a memory. In general such stochastic models are known as a Markov process, in which the probability of an event depends only on the current state. Such processes are used in finance and economy to interpret a variety of different phenomena such as dynamics of macroeconomics and Markov Switching Multifractal models, see e.g. [156]. Another goal of the analysis of Markov processes is to make prediction, based on asset prices, taking into account the present value of the asset, regardless of its history.

Let us go back and consider the Gaussian distribution of the noise in the cumulative production. Another interesting problem is to modify the model and consider a chain without memory, i.e. the sum of the past noise in the cumulative production is removed. That means we replace

$$y_i = gi + a_1 + a_2 \dots a_i \quad \text{by} \quad y_i = gi + a_i. \quad (113)$$

In the new model, the first component of y is the deterministic or trend component and the second part is the stochastic component.

The first model described in the subsection 4.1.1 was difference stationary: its first difference has a constant mean and variance. It's called integrated of order 1 or $I(1)$. We could show that $\log Z$ is $I(1)$ if $\log Q$ is $I(1)$, which was non-trivial. In statistics and probability theory this approach is called unit root test, which tests the stationarity or trend stationarity in the sample. More generally, the integrand of the order d or $I(d)$ simply implies that after d times differentiation the series will be stationary.

Now let us suppose that Q follows the new model without considering the past noise. This new model is called trend stationary because if we remove the trend then it is stationary. We do not need to differentiate to obtain stationarity, because noise does not accumulate. So it is an integrated of order 0 or $I(0)$. It is a challenging question in economy whether the integrand is of order 1 or 0, which leads to the huge literature of the unit root tests. Let us now calculate the volatility for the cumulative production by using the steepest descent method for this new model.

We follow again the same procedure as in subsection 4.1.1, with the difference that in this case the process is trend stationary as described above.

We compute the expectation value of $z = \log Z$, where

$$Z_t = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^t e^{y_i},$$

assuming that the distribution of y_t is

$$P(y_t = Y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_a^2 t}} \exp\left(-\frac{(Y - gt)^2}{2\sigma_a^2 t}\right).$$

This leads to the (multiple) integral (the range of integration variables y_i are $(-\infty, \infty)$)

$$\int \log Z \prod_{i=1}^t \frac{dy_i}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_a^2 i}} \exp\left(-\frac{(y_i - gi)^2}{2\sigma_a^2 i}\right).$$

In analogy, we apply saddle point method which assumes that $\sigma_a^2 \ll 1$.

It is convenient to make change of variables $y_i \rightarrow \sqrt{i}y_i$ after which our integral becomes

$$\int \log Z \prod_{i=1}^t \frac{dy_i}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_a^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(y_i - g\sqrt{i})^2}{2\sigma_a^2}\right),$$

but Z now is given by

$$Z(y_1, \dots, y_t) = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^t e^{\sqrt{i}y_i}.$$

The saddle point is defined from the system of equations ($n = 1, 2, \dots, t$ and $\partial_n \equiv \partial/\partial y_n$)

$$\partial_n \left(\log(\log Z) - \frac{(y_n - g\sqrt{n})^2}{2\sigma_a^2} \right) = 0,$$

or

$$\frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z} - \frac{y_n - g\sqrt{n}}{\sigma_a^2} = 0,$$

which we rewrite as

$$y_n = g\sqrt{n} + \sigma_a^2 \frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z}.$$

Since we are going to make calculations up to order σ_a^2 , it is legitimate to substitute in second term $y_i = g\sqrt{i}$. Thus for the saddle point (y_1^*, \dots, y_t^*) we get

$$y_n^* = g\sqrt{n} + \sigma_a^2 \frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z} \Big|_{y_n=g\sqrt{n}} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4).$$

Expanding up to order σ_a^2 for the $\log Z(y_i^*)$ we get

$$\log Z(y_i^*) = \log Z + \sigma_a^2 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \Big|_{y_i=g\sqrt{i}} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (114)$$

The contribution of the Gaussian term:

$$\exp\left(-\frac{(y_i - g\sqrt{i})^2}{2\sigma_a^2}\right)\Bigg|_{y_i=y_i^*} = 1 - \frac{\sigma_a^2 \sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2}{2 Z^2 \log^2 Z} \Bigg|_{y_i=g\sqrt{i}} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (115)$$

Below we should calculate the matrix of quadratic fluctuations. For second derivatives we get

$$\partial_n \partial_m \log \log Z = \frac{\partial_n \partial_m Z}{Z \log Z} - \frac{\partial_n Z \partial_m Z (1 + \log Z)}{Z^2 \log^2 Z}.$$

Incorporating this (with factor 1/2 coming from the Taylor's formula for the second order coefficient) with the initial Gaussian term, for the matrix of quadratic form we get

$$G_{n,m} = \frac{1}{2\sigma_a^2} \left(\delta_{n,m} + \sigma_a^2 \left(-\frac{\partial_n \partial_m Z}{Z \log Z} + \frac{(1 + \log Z) \partial_n Z \partial_m Z}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \right) \Bigg|_{y_i=g\sqrt{i}} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4) \right).$$

Recall now the Gauss formula for the integral

$$\int \exp\left(-\sum_{n,m=1}^t \xi_n G_{n,m} \xi_m\right) \prod_{i=1}^t d\xi_i = (\det G)^{-1/2} \pi^{t/2}.$$

Using

$$\det G = \exp(tr \log G),$$

we up to desired order we get

$$\begin{aligned} (2\sigma_a^2)^{-t/2} (\det G)^{-1/2} &= \\ &= 1 + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^t \partial_i^2 Z}{Z \log Z} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2 (1 + \log Z)}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \right) \Bigg|_{y_i=g\sqrt{i}} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (116)$$

Multiplying all factors given by Eqs. (114), (115), (116) we finally get

$$E(\log Z) = \log Z_0 + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \left(\frac{\sum_{i=0}^t i e^{ig}}{Z_0} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t i e^{2ig}}{Z_0^2} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4),$$

where

$$Z_0 \equiv \sum_{i=0}^t e^{ig} = \frac{1 - e^{g(t+1)}}{1 - e^g}.$$

We can rewrite above expression as

$$E(\log Z) = \log Z_0 + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{4Z_0^2} \partial_g (Z_0^2 - Z_2) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4), \quad (117)$$

where we have introduced notation

$$Z_2 = \sum_{i=0}^t e^{2ig} = \frac{1 - e^{2g(t+1)}}{1 - e^{2g}}. \quad (118)$$

If $g < 0$, in large $t \rightarrow \infty$ limit

$$Z_0 \rightarrow \frac{1}{1 - e^g}, \quad Z_2 \rightarrow \frac{1}{1 - e^{2g}},$$

hence

$$E(\log Z)|_{t \rightarrow \infty} = \log \frac{1}{1 - e^g} + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \left(\frac{e^g}{1 - e^g} - \frac{e^{2g}}{(1 + e^g)^2} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4).$$

In the opposite case $g > 0$ we'll have

$$Z_0 \rightarrow \frac{e^{g(t+1)}}{e^g - 1}, \quad Z_2 \rightarrow \frac{e^{2g(t+1)}}{e^{2g} - 1},$$

which leads to

$$\begin{aligned} E(\log Z)|_{t \rightarrow \infty} = g - \log(e^g - 1) &+ \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{(e^g + 1)^2} + \frac{1}{1 - e^g} \right) \\ &+ t \left(g + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{e^g + 1} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (119)$$

We see that drift gets correction and becomes

$$g + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{e^g + 1}. \quad (120)$$

Now let us calculate the expectation value $E(\log^2 Z)$.

The integral we have to compute is

$$\int \log^2 Z \prod_{i=1}^t \frac{dy_i}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_a^2}} \exp -\frac{(y_i - g\sqrt{i})^2}{2\sigma_a^2}.$$

The saddle point equations

$$\partial_n \left(2 \log(\log Z) - \frac{(y_n - g\sqrt{n})^2}{2\sigma_a^2} \right) = 0,$$

or

$$2 \frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z} - \frac{y_n - g\sqrt{n}}{\sigma_a^2} = 0,$$

which gives

$$y_n = g\sqrt{n} + 2\sigma_a^2 \frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z}.$$

As in previous case in second term we can substitute $y_i = g\sqrt{i}$ and for the saddle point (y_1^*, \dots, y_t^*) we get

$$y_n^* = g\sqrt{n} + 2\sigma_a^2 \frac{\partial_n Z}{Z \log Z} \Big|_{y_n=g\sqrt{n}} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4).$$

Up to order σ_a^2 expansion for $\log^2 Z(y_i^*)$:

$$\log Z(y_i^*) = \log^2 Z + 4\sigma_a^2 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2}{Z^2} \Big|_{y_i=g\sqrt{i}} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (121)$$

The contribution of the Gaussian term is

$$\exp\left(-\frac{(y_i - g\sqrt{i})^2}{2\sigma_a^2}\right) \Big|_{y_i=y_i^*} = 1 - 2\sigma_a^2 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \Big|_{y_i=g\sqrt{i}} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (122)$$

The matrix of quadratic fluctuations is

$$G_{n,m} = \frac{1}{2\sigma_a^2} \left(\delta_{n,m} + 2\sigma_a^2 \left(-\frac{\partial_n \partial_m Z}{Z \log Z} + \frac{(1 + \log Z) \partial_n Z \partial_m Z}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \right) \Big|_{y_i=g\sqrt{i}} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4) \right).$$

Up to desired order we get

$$\begin{aligned} (2\sigma_a^2)^{-t/2} (\det G)^{-1/2} &= \\ &= 1 + \sigma_a^2 \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^t \partial_i^2 Z}{Z \log Z} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t (\partial_i Z)^2 (1 + \log Z)}{Z^2 \log^2 Z} \right) \Big|_{y_i=g\sqrt{i}} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (123)$$

Multiplying all factors we finally get

$$E(\log^2 Z) = \log^2 Z_0 + \sigma_a^2 \left(\frac{(\log Z_0 - 1) \sum_{i=1}^t i e^{2ig}}{Z_0^2} + \frac{\log Z_0 \sum_{i=0}^t i e^{ig}}{Z_0} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4),$$

or

$$E(\log^2 Z) = \log^2 Z_0 + \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \left(\frac{(\log Z_0 - 1) \partial_g Z_2}{Z_0^2} + \partial_g \log^2 Z_0 \right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (124)$$

It remains to calculate the variance

$$E(\log^2 Z) - (E(\log Z))^2 = \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \frac{\partial_g Z_2}{Z_0^2} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4), \quad (125)$$

Explicitly we get

$$\begin{aligned} & E(\log^2 Z) - (E(\log Z))^2 \\ &= \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \frac{e^{2g} - e^{2g(t+1)} + t(e^{2g(t+2)} - e^{2g(t+1)})}{(e^g + 1)^2 (e^{g(t+1)} - 1)^2} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (126)$$

If $g > 0$ and $t \rightarrow \infty$ we get

$$E(\log^2 Z) - (E(\log Z))^2 = \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \frac{(e^{2g} - 1)t - 1}{(e^g + 1)^2} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (127)$$

In a similar way we compute the quantity

$$\begin{aligned} & E(\log Z(t) \log Z(t+1)) - E(\log Z(t))E(\log Z(t+1)) \\ &= \sigma_a^2 \frac{\partial_g Z_2(t)}{2Z_0(t)Z_0(t+1)} + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \end{aligned} \quad (128)$$

Remind that (see (118))

$$Z_0(t) = \frac{1 - e^{g(t+1)}}{1 - e^g}; \quad Z_2(t) = \frac{1 - e^{2g(t+1)}}{1 - e^{2g}}.$$

Incorporating this result with previous ones, for the variance of $\Delta \log Z$ we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) = \\ &= E((\log Z(t+1) - \log Z(t))^2) - (E(\log Z(t+1) - \log Z(t)))^2 = \\ &= \text{Var}(\log Z(t+1)) + \text{Var}(\log Z(t)) - 2(E(\log Z(t) \log Z(t+1)) \\ &\quad - E(\log Z(t))E(\log Z(t+1))) \\ &= \frac{\sigma_a^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial_g Z_2(t)}{Z_0(t)^2} + \frac{\partial_g Z_2(t+1)}{Z_0(t+1)^2} - \frac{2\partial_g Z_2(t)}{Z_0(t)Z_0(t+1)} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (129)$$

As already mentioned for $g > 0$ in large t limit

$$Z_0(t) \approx \frac{e^{g(t+1)}}{e^g - 1}; \quad Z_2(t) \approx \frac{e^{2g(t+1)}}{e^{2g} - 1},$$

which leads to

$$\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) = \frac{\sigma_a^2 (e^g - 1)^2 (2 + e^g + 2(e^g + 1)t)}{e^g (e^g + 1)^2}. \quad (130)$$

Here as it is visible we see the dependency on t which implies that the process is not station-

ary. It is possible with the same procedure to check higher order derivatives and to analyze the root test of the process. The finding tells us that if we consider the production process as a chain without memory in the noise, then the variance is not stationary. In reality the variance should decay and has a finite limit for $t \rightarrow \infty$, but in this model the variance goes to infinity for large t . The behavior of this model is qualitatively different from that studied in the section 4.2, and also different from empirical findings. Therefore we discard the further investigation of this model. Note that in contrast, the first difference of the model obtained in the section 4.2 has a constant mean and variance, which is in turn non-trivial and important result for economy.

4.6 Skewness and kurtosis of the production processes

It is also interesting to calculate the third and fourth cumulants (polynomial combinations of the moments) of the distribution functions, as the additional knowledge characterizes more closely the distribution function and quantifies derivations from for instance normal distributions. The important characteristics of cumulants is their additive feature, for sums of independent random variables. It is notable, that for the Gaussian distribution all cumulants of order larger than two are identically zero.

In probability theory and statistics the third cumulant or skewness describes asymmetry of the probability distribution about its mean. If the skew is negative, then the tail on the left side of the probability density function is heavier than that on the right side. Conversely, positive skew shows that the tail on the right hand side is heavier than on the left hand side [157].

As mentioned above and according to the definition of the skewness, it is obvious that the skewness of the normal distribution is zero. But there are often cases where the distributions are not symmetric and skewness can describe this asymmetry and is given by the following expression:

$$c_3 = \frac{\langle (x - m)^3 \rangle}{\sigma^3}, \quad (131)$$

where m denotes the mean and σ^2 is the variance of the process. Skewness plays a crucial role in finance and investing strategies. Stock prices and asset returns have mostly either positive or negative skew. Knowing which way data skews, an investor can better assess whether it is time to invest or not [158].

In analogy to the concept of skewness, kurtosis or the fourth moment also describes the shape of the probability distribution. The concept is related to the tail of the distribution. Kurtosis also quantifies the deviation of a distribution from Gaussian, i.e it can be understood as a

measure of the distance between a given distribution and a normal distribution and is given by the following formula:

$$c_4 = \frac{\langle (x - m)^4 \rangle}{\sigma^4} - 3. \quad (132)$$

We derive here the third and fourth moments of the distribution function of the production process. As discussed above the distribution function of ρ_a has the mean $c_1 = 0$, variance $c_2 = \sigma_a^2$ and skewness $c_3 = 0$. Similarly we define for the distribution function of ρ_{y_t} the mean, variance and skewness as follows: $c_1 = b_t$, $c_2 = \sigma_t^2$, $c_3 = s_t$.

For the mean, variance, and skewness of the convolution $\rho_a * \rho_{y_t}$ of the distributions, we have consequently the following expressions: $c_1 = b_t$, $c_2 = \sigma_a^2 + \sigma_t^2$ and $c_3 = s_t$ and similarly for the kurtosis we have $c_4(\rho_a * \rho_{y_t}) = c_4(\rho_a) + c_4(\rho_{y_t})$. Here we use the nice additivity feature of cumulants under convolution.

The main problem to solve is to understand how skewness and variance behave under the variable transformation. For the latter one we get the following expression

$$\sqrt{m_2} = |f'(k)|\sqrt{m_2}, \quad (133)$$

where, m_2 is the second moment, $k = -\log(1 - e^{-g})$ and $f(x) = \log(\exp(x) - 1) + g$, $f(-\log(1 - e^{-g})) = -\log(1 - e^{-g})$.

Furthermore, using the variable transformation for the kurtosis of ρ_{y_∞} and $m = -\log(1 - e^{-g})$ we obtain the following

$$c_4(\rho_{y_\infty}) = \frac{e^{-4g}}{1 - e^{-4g}} c_4(\rho_a), \quad (134)$$

where $c_4(\rho_a) \simeq -3\sigma_a^4$

Hence we get

$$c_4(\rho_{\Delta z}) = \frac{g^3}{4} c_4(\rho_a) = -3\sigma_a^2 \frac{g^3}{4}. \quad (135)$$

In analogy for the skewness of the distribution we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} c_3(\rho_{\Delta z}) &= (e^g - 1)^3 3\sigma_a^4 \left[\frac{1}{(1 - e^{-2g})^2} - \frac{(1 - e^{-g})^4}{(1 - e^{-4g})^2} \right] = \\ &= 3\sigma_a^4 e^{4g} \frac{e^g - 1}{(e^g + 1)^2} \left[1 - \frac{(e^g - 1)^4}{(e^{2g} + 1)^2} \right] = \frac{3}{4} g \sigma_a^4. \end{aligned} \quad (136)$$

The analytical result shows that the skewness for our case is positive, which coincides with results shown in plots, because the tails of the plots (see, e.g. figures 14 and 15), are heavier on the right hand side.

The saddle point approximation is an appropriate method when we deal with a distribution function like the Gaussian. But as discussed above, in general distribution functions have non-vanishing skewness and kurtosis. In this section the goal was to calculate such corrections to the Gaussian and the saddle point approximation.

4.7 Aggregation of capital stocks by depreciation

Most countries estimate capital stocks from investment, which is drawn upon the perpetual inventory method. In business and industrial activities it is important to know how the price of a particular commodity declines over time passing by. The amount by which the capital stock decreases in the period of time is called depreciation rate. Otherwise said, as years pass by, the value of stock price usually falls and the rate of depreciation is the descriptor for this change [159].

This phenomenon occurs because most capital assets have finite lifetime, due to some reasons such as repair costs are rising, so keeping them is not economical; there is an immense technological progress in the market, which leads to an innovation of the market, and finally some assets are simply destroyed in the period of time.

In calculating depreciation, researchers developed a number of methods, aimed to estimate how asset values decline during their lifetimes. In the vast majority of alternatives, mostly the following three depreciation methods are used: straight-line (if asset prices are falling by a constant amount each year), geometric (if asset prices are falling by a constant rate each year) and sum-of-the-years-digits. These methods presume, that the systematic decline in the value of an asset over a period of time is based only on the initial value of the asset and its expected lifetime [160, 161].

The geometric depreciation method is applicable for the cases, where the ability for producing capital services for the given assets reduces by the largest amount in the first year. Thus the geometric depreciation is not a useful method for the cases, where assets will have an increasing amount of preservation as they get older.

The sum-of-the-years-digits depreciation method is also based on the concept that the largest fall in efficiency is at the beginning of the asset's service life. The main difference between these two methods is that there is a huge change on the initial and final asset price in the latter method. In contrast to these two methods, the straight-line depreciation method shows a linear decline in an age of efficiency, i.e. the asset price falls by the same absolute amount for each period.

We are going to use some of the techniques we introduced for the study of cumulative production, aimed to construct the relationship between the capital and the investment. We denote the capital of the stock by Z_t at time t and gross investment at any time by Q_t . By

assuming geometric depreciation at a constant rate d we can rewrite the capital stock at time Z_{t+1} as a function of its previous value and the investment as follows

$$Z_{t+1} = (1 - d)Z_t + Q_{t+1}, \quad 0 < d < 1. \quad (137)$$

The strategy is to reduce the new problem to that one studied in section 4.2.

In previous model we had:

$$Z_t := \sum_{j=0}^t Q_j, \quad Q_t := e^{gt} e^{a_1} \dots e^{a_t}. \quad (138)$$

Otherwise said, in the old model we have:

$$Z_{t+1} = Z_t + Q_{t+1}, \quad (139)$$

where $d = 0$ and the solution for volatility is also known:

$$\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) = \sigma_a^2 \tanh\left(\frac{g}{2}\right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (140)$$

Now it is desirable to obtain the solution for (137).

For this purpose we replace $Z_t := (1 - d)^t \hat{Z}_t$. Let us substitute this in Eq. (137), so we get

$$(1 - d)^{(t+1)} \hat{Z}_{t+1} = (1 - d)^{(t+1)} \hat{Z}_t + Q_{t+1}. \quad (141)$$

By dividing the above equation by $(1 - d)^{(t+1)}$, we obtain

$$\hat{Z}_{t+1} = \hat{Z}_t + (1 - d)^{(-t-1)} Q_{t+1}. \quad (142)$$

Let us denote

$$\hat{Q}_{t+1} := (1 - d)^{-t-1} Q_{t+1}. \quad (143)$$

Thus we have

$$\hat{Z}_{t+1} := \hat{Z}_t + \hat{Q}_{t+1}, \quad (144)$$

our old formula, namely Eq. (139).

From Eq. (142) we can easily read that

$$\hat{Q}_t = (1 - d)^{-t} Q_t \quad (145)$$

Let us substitute Eq. (138) in (143), so we get

$$\hat{Q}_t = (1-d)^{-t} e^{gt} e^{a_1} \dots e^{a_t} = e^{(g-\ln(1-d)t)} e^{a_1} \dots e^{a_t} = e^{\tilde{g}t} e^{a_1} \dots e^{a_t}, \quad (146)$$

where $\tilde{g} := g - \ln(1-d)$. We see that \hat{Z}_t satisfies the old equation with $Q \rightarrow \hat{Q}_t$.

So, our main analytical result, for the volatility of the cumulative capital, for $g > 0$ in the large t limit is

$$\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) = \sigma_a^2 \tanh\left(\frac{\tilde{g}}{2}\right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4), \quad (147)$$

where $\tilde{g} := g - \ln(1-d)$.

If we consider the case $|d| \ll 1$, we get $\tilde{g} := g + d$. Hence, for this case we have

$$\text{Var}(\Delta \log Z) = \sigma_a^2 \tanh\left(\frac{g+d}{2}\right) + \mathcal{O}(\sigma_a^4). \quad (148)$$

We find counterintuitively, that Z_t grows less with t for $0 < d < 1$ than in section 4.2, but the variance of $\Delta \log Z$ is larger.

The depreciation stems from the companies investing activities and strategies and has an influence on the asset value. Furthermore, in order to be able to calculate the current capital stock, one needs the dataset of the investment data, information about the initial capital stock and the rate of depreciation of the current capital stock.

In fact here we showed how to reduce the more general problem to the special case we treated before in section 4.2, by deriving the full solution and performing the calculations for a completely new area and problem. Eq. (148) shows how the volatility of aggregated capital stock is related to the volatility of the investment and depreciation, by opening the research of the predictive power of capital through an investment.

Part V

Exact probability distribution functions of Parrondo's games

5 Exact probability distribution of Parrondo's games

The Parrondo's games are related to Brownian ratchets [72]-[76] with applications in physics, biology, engineering and financial risk.

Phrased in simple words, the phenomenon describes games, each with higher probability of losing than winning. The Parrondo's paradox suggests that it is possible to obtain the winning strategy after playing the games alternately. Otherwise said, an agent tosses biased coins using one of two strategies (games), and both strategies are losing. In some cases a random combination of the losing games is a winning game.

The phenomenon is fundamentally related to portfolio optimization [81], and corresponds to the "volatility pumping" strategy in portfolio optimization. For a two-asset portfolio one half of the capital is kept in the first asset, the other half in the second asset with high volatility [82]. Applications have also been linked to quantum models [162, 163], where the classical coin toss is replaced by the measurement of a qubit. One of the studies is by Meyer et al. [164] in which they show that Parrondo's paradox can be modelled by probabilistic lattice gas automata. Their work introduces a quantum analogue of the ratcheting mechanism seen in the original Parrondo's game, with possible applications in quantum computing. Further investigations on quantum Parrondo's games [165]-[168] yielded other variants, in the process shedding light on the roles of entanglement and coherence on game outcomes. Almeida et al. have considered how two chaotic systems can give rise to order, in the form of quadratic maps. This is related to Parrondo's paradox, having a lose + lose = win situation [169]. Other phenomena like the presence of stable states within chaos [170, 171] have been understood under the framework of Parrondo's games. The paradox has also been considered in reliability theory. Starting with subunits of a system being less reliable than the subunits of another system, Crescenzo has shown that by randomly choosing units from these two systems can allow one to obtain a system that is more reliable than the initial two [172].

In evolutionary biology, Wolf et al. have found that if different environmental states are selected for different cell states, and if cells are unlikely to sense environmental transitions or are subject to long signal transduction delays relative to the time-scale of environmental change, then a time-varying environment can select for random phase variation (RPV) [173]. They noted that the success of RPV can be understood as a variant of Parrondo's paradox [173], in which random alternations between losing strategies (in this case, cells that choose the wrong phase variation or sequence of variations) produce a winning strategy. Separately, the evolution of less accurate sensors has been modelled and explained in terms of the paradox [174]. In ecology, the periodic alternation of certain organisms between nomadic and colonial behaviors has also been suggested as a manifestation of the paradox [179]. Recently, there is an intriguing finding of Parrondo-like phenomena in a Bayesian approach to the modelling

of the work by a jury [83]: the unanimous decision of its members has a low confidence. The developments of Parrondo's paradox have cut across many disciplines, with a wide range of possible applications.

Another interesting variant of Parrondo's paradox is the Allison mixture [89]-[90], where random mixing of two random sequences creates autocorrelation [90]. The Allison mixture has some resemblance to the thermodynamic picture of the Feynman-Smoluchowski ratchet: at equilibrium there is detailed balance, time-reversibility, and no net displacement; whereas out of equilibrium detailed balance is broken, with time-irreversibility leading to net displacement [90, 80]. It is worth noting that the Allison mixture process mixes two random sequences in a time-irreversible way *only* when symmetry in the governing transition probabilities is broken. Here we refer to [71, 80, 91] for more information on the Allison mixture. There have been discussions to link the Allison mixture to applications in encryption and optimization of file compression [89].

After this introduction part let us begin with the explanation of the process by focusing on the probability of capital and variances of distributions: In the case of Brownian ratchets, a particle moves in a potential, which randomly changes between two options. For each there is a detailed balance condition. However, for random switches between the two potentials, there is on average a directed motion.

The state of the system is characterized by the current value of the capital X , and the choice of the strategy. X is defined on a one-dimensional axis with discrete points, a "chain". For the study of Parrondo's paradox we consider the probability of a position corresponding to the probability of capital. In analogy to ratchets, there may be a periodicity M in the rules, how capital X can increase or decrease. This version corresponds to a particle moving on a ladder geometry with several rungs [180]. Originally $M = 3$ games were considered, then $M = 2$ versions of Parrondo's games were constructed [181], [73]. For the history dependent versions of the game the current rules of the game depend on the past, whether there was growth of capital in the previous rounds or not.

As the variances of distributions (volatilities) are important in economics, we calculated the variance for the history independent case with specific parameters in [182]. And vice versa, for obtaining the unknown parameters of a model that describes empirical data, the complete distributions have to be available. This is the problem we address here by applying a Fourier transform technique to solve exactly the probability distribution function. This approach allows for an efficient calculation of the long time asymptotics from saddle point contributions. We discover that under certain conditions sub-leading saddle points become degenerate in absolute value with the leading saddle point. Still, the degenerate saddle points differ in phases which leads to strong fluctuations.

We apply this method to random walks on chains and ladders corresponding to capital

dependent Parrondo's models. We calculate the entire probability distribution for the capital, then solve the same problem for history dependent games.

In passing we revisit the grounds of Parrondo's paradox. We calculate from our efficient formulas for the capital growth examples of two losing strategies that jointly but randomly applied yield a winning strategy.

5.1 A biased discrete space and time random walk

As an illustration let us consider the discrete time random walk on a chain, where the probability of right and left jumps are p and q , respectively. We can write the master equation for the probability $P(n, t)$ at position n after t steps:

$$P(n, t + 1) = pP(n - 1, t) + qP(n + 1, t) + (1 - p - q)P(n, t). \quad (149)$$

The initial distribution is $P(n, 0) = \delta_{n,0}$.

For the motion on the infinite axis we can always write a Fourier transform like

$$\begin{aligned} P(n, t) &= \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dk e^{ikn} \bar{P}(k, t), \\ \bar{P}(k, t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_n P(n, t) e^{-ikn}. \end{aligned} \quad (150)$$

For the initial distribution the Fourier transform is $\bar{P}(k, 0) = 1/2\pi$.

By considering the recursion relation for $\bar{P}(k, t)$, for the link hand side of the Eq. (178) we have:

$$P(n, t + 1) = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dk e^{ikn} \bar{P}(k, t + 1),$$

and the right hand side is equal to:

$$\begin{aligned} pP(n - 1, t) + qP(n + 1, t) + (1 - p - q)P(n, t) &= \\ = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dk (pe^{-ik} + qe^{ik} + 1 - p - q) e^{ikn} \bar{P}(k, t). \end{aligned}$$

Here we used:

$$P(n - 1, t) = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dk \underbrace{e^{ik(n-1)}}_{e^{-ik} \cdot e^{ikn}} \bar{P}(k, t).$$

Eq. (149) transforms into

$$\bar{P}(k, t+1) = [pe^{-ik} + qe^{ik} + (1-p-q)] \bar{P}(k, t). \quad (151)$$

Hence we get the following solution:

$$\tilde{P}(k, t) = (pe^{-ik} + qe^{ik} + 1-p-q)^t \bar{P}(k, 0).$$

We obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P}(k, t) &= \lambda^t(k) \cdot \bar{P}(k, 0), \\ \lambda(k) &= [pe^{-ik} + qe^{ik} + (1-p-q)]. \end{aligned} \quad (152)$$

As λ is a linear polynomial in e^{ik} and e^{-ik} , λ^t is a polynomial with monomials ranging from e^{-tik} to e^{tik} .

The Fourier transform from momentum to spatial representation yields

$$\begin{aligned} P(n, t) &= \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dk e^{tV(ik)+ikn} \bar{P}(k, 0), \\ V(\kappa) &:= \ln [pe^{-\kappa} + qe^{\kappa} + (1-p-q)], \end{aligned} \quad (153)$$

where we defined the function $V(\kappa)$. Note that V is not a potential and for the large time we only need the expansion to the second order. Using that λ^t has a finite expansion in powers of e^{ik} we obtain with $\bar{P}(k, 0) = 1/2\pi$

$$P(n, t) = \frac{1}{2t} \sum_{m=1}^{2t} e^{tV(im\pi/t)+imn\pi/t}. \quad (154)$$

Also for the study of more involved models, we will use both representations (153), (154). Note that Eqs. (153) and (154) are exact for any t and n . By use of the saddle point approximation we derive the large t and $n = xt$ asymptotics. We are allowed to move the integration contour because of the analytic dependence of the integrand on k resulting in ($\kappa = ik$)

$$P(n, t) = \frac{\exp[tu(x)]}{\sqrt{2\pi t V''(\kappa)}}, \quad (155)$$

and

$$x = -V'(\kappa), \quad u(x) = V(\kappa) + \kappa x.$$

As $u(x)$ is the Legendre transform of $-V(\kappa)$, we also have $V''(k) = -1/u''(x)$ and hence

$$P(n, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi t}} \exp [tu(x) + 1/2 \log |u''(x)|].$$

Let us assume an expansion for $V(\kappa)$

$$V(\kappa) = -r\kappa + K\kappa^2/2 + \mathcal{O}(\kappa^3). \quad (156)$$

In general the expression is not Gaussian, but for the large time limit it approaches a Gaussian.

In fact the expression (153) yields

$$r = p - q$$

and

$$K = q + p - (p - q)^2.$$

From (156) we obtain the Legendre transform

$$u(x) = -\frac{(x - r)^2}{2K} + \mathcal{O}((x - r)^3),$$

where the high order terms vanish in case of vanishing high order terms in (156). In the long time limit, these higher order terms can be neglected and a Gaussian distribution evolves. Higher order terms in $V(\kappa)$, namely $\mathcal{O}(\kappa^3)$ leads to higher order terms in $u(x)$.

For the case $p + q = 1$ we get a nice expression:

$$u(x) = -\frac{1+x}{2} \ln \frac{1+x}{2p} - \frac{1-x}{2} \ln \frac{1-x}{2q}.$$

It then follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle n \rangle &= rt, \\ \langle (n - \langle n \rangle)^2 \rangle &= Kt. \end{aligned} \quad (157)$$

In this scalar case we do not observe any Parrondo effect. Note that the rates are given by $r = p_i - q_i$. If p_1 and p_2 are losing, $p_1 - q_1 < 0$ and $p_2 - q_2 < 0$, then also $\frac{p_1+p_2}{2} - \frac{q_1+q_2}{2} < 0$, which is the rate for the combined strategy with $p = \frac{p_1+p_2}{2}$ and $q = \frac{q_1+q_2}{2}$.

5.2 Random walks with periodicity

Consider the case of a random walk on an axis, using rules with period M . We divide the entire x axis in intervals of length M , $[(n-1)M, nM[$, and label points by (n, l) where $l = \text{Mod}(X, M)$. We represent the sets of p_X (the discrete probability distribution of the capital value) by $P_l(n, t)$, $0 \leq l < M$. The integer t represents time. This bookkeeping allows us to consider the geometry with periodicity M as a multi-rung ladder or as a chain of unit cells containing M points.

We study the following master equation [183]

$$P_l(n, t+1) = p_{l_-} P_{l_-}(\hat{n}, t) + q_{l_+} P_{l_+}(\bar{n}, t) + (1 - p_l - q_l) P_l(n, t), \quad (158)$$

where $l_- = \text{Mod}(l-1, M)$, $l_+ = \text{Mod}(l+1, M)$, $\hat{n} = n$ for $l-1 \geq 0$ and $\hat{n} = n-1$ for $l-1 < 0$; $\bar{n} = n$ for $l+1 < M$ and $\bar{n} = n+1$ for $l+1 > M$. Thus the model is characterized by the parameters p_l, q_l , where p_l and q_l are the probabilities to win and lose for capital X with $l = \text{Mod}(X, M)$. The model comes from the literature and the goal is to analyze the distribution function of this process as we did in section 5.1.

Again we consider the Fourier transform

$$P_l(n, t) = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dk e^{ikn} \bar{P}_l(k, t), \quad (159)$$

and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P}_l(k, t+1) &= p_{l_-} e^{ik(\hat{n}-n)} \bar{P}_{l_-}(k, t) + q_{l_+} e^{ik(\bar{n}-n)} P_{l_+}(k, t) + (1 - (p_l + q_l)) \bar{P}_l(k, t) \\ &\equiv \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \hat{Q}_{lm}(ik) \bar{P}_m(k, t). \end{aligned} \quad (160)$$

Using the eigenvalues and eigenvectors $\lambda_m(\kappa), v_{ml}(\kappa)$ ($m = 0, \dots, M-1$), of the matrix $\hat{Q}(\kappa)$, we find

$$\bar{P}_l(n, t) = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dk e^{ikn} \sum_m c_m \exp[tV_m] v_{ml}, \quad (161)$$

where $V_m(\kappa) := \ln(\lambda_m(\kappa))$. The factors $c_m(\kappa)$ are determined by the initial distribution. For using Eq. (155), we choose as $V(\kappa)$ the eigenvalue function $V_m(\kappa)$ with the largest saddle point. For generic parameters and close to the maximum of the distribution $u(x)$, the choice is unique. Saddle points with smaller value do not contribute to the large time asymptotics. However, we will encounter the possibility of several eigenvalues degenerate in absolute value. To compare our results for the gain/loss rate with the formulas in [181] we have to multiply

the rate r in Eq. (157) for the case of the multi-rung ladder with a factor M , as one step in n in our approach equals M ordinary steps.

The periodicity reflects the capital independent strategy of portfolio management. Ladder geometries with rungs that contain $p > 1$ points represent invested capital in one out of p different stocks. Motions along the ladder represent gain or loss, motions along rungs represent change of the composition of the portfolio.

5.3 The eigenvalues ± 1

Next we investigate more closely the case of zero probability for holding the capital at the current value, i.e. $p_l + q_l = 1$ for all l in (160).

Consider first the case of odd M : $\hat{Q}(0)$ has one eigenvalue $+1$ with left eigenstate $(1, 1, 1, 1\dots)$, and $\hat{Q}(\pi i)$ has one eigenvalue -1 with left eigenstate $(1, -1, 1, -1\dots)$. Hence, in Fourier representation the two “momenta” $\kappa = 0$ and $\kappa = \pi i$ contribute to the asymptotic behaviour. Let us now consider the matrices $\hat{Q}(\kappa)$ and $\hat{Q}(\kappa + \pi i)$ for arbitrary κ . It is easy to see that the spectra are simply related. Let $(x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots)^T$ be a right eigenvector of $\hat{Q}(\kappa)$ with eigenvalue $\lambda(\kappa)$, then $(x_0, -x_1, x_2, \dots)^T$ is a right eigenvector of $\hat{Q}(\kappa + \pi i)$ with eigenvalue $-\lambda(\kappa)$.

Let us assume an expansion like Eq. (156) for the leading $V(\kappa)$ near $\kappa = 0$, then

$$V(\pi + \kappa) = \pi i + r\kappa + K\kappa^2/2. \quad (162)$$

Let v^+ and v^- be the right eigenstates of $\hat{Q}(0)$ and $\hat{Q}(\pi i)$ with eigenvalues $+1$ and -1 . There are constants α and β such that

$$P_l(n, t) = \frac{\alpha v_l^+ + (-1)^{n+t} \beta v_l^-}{\sqrt{2\pi K t}} e^{-\frac{(n-rt)^2}{2Kt}}. \quad (163)$$

We see oscillations caused by the rapid sign change of the second term. The coefficients α and β are determined by the initial probability distribution. If this was peaked at $n = l = 0$ then $\alpha = \beta$ (with v^+ and v^- related as pointed out above). In this case $P_l(n, t)$ is non-zero (zero) for even (odd) $l + n + t$.

Consider now the case of even M . Here, $\hat{Q}(0)$ has one eigenvalue 1 with left eigenstate $(1, 1, 1, 1\dots)$ and one eigenvalue -1 with left eigenstate $(1, -1, 1, -1\dots)$. Hence, only the “momentum” $\kappa = 0$ contributes in the Fourier representation to the asymptotic behaviour, but with two eigenvalues. Let $(x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots)^T$ be a right eigenvector of $\hat{Q}(\kappa)$ with eigenvalue $\lambda(\kappa)$, then $(x_0, -x_1, x_2, \dots)^T$ is also a right eigenvector of $\hat{Q}(\kappa)$, but with eigenvalue $-\lambda(\kappa)$.

Now we find similar to the case above

$$P_l(n, t) = \frac{\alpha v_l^+ + (-1)^t \beta v_l^-}{\sqrt{2\pi Kt}} e^{-\frac{(n-rt)^2}{2Kt}}. \quad (164)$$

Note that the oscillating factor does not depend on n . For a probability initially peaked at $n = l = 0$ we find $P_l(n, t)$ is non-zero (zero) for even (odd) $l + t$.

The findings in both cases, odd M and even M , can however be summarized: $P_l(n, t)$ is non-zero (zero) for even (odd) $l + nM + t$.

It is quite interesting to consider the quantity

$$\hat{P}(n, t) = \sum_{l=0}^{M-1} P_l(n, t). \quad (165)$$

It shows non-zero oscillations in dependence on n and t for odd M . Such oscillations do not exist for even M . The reason for this is easily understood: the term entering $\hat{P}(n, t)$ with a $(-1)^t$ factor is $\sum_l v_l^-$. This is the scalar product of $(1, 1, 1, 1, \dots)$ with $(x_0, -x_1, x_2, -x_3, \dots)^T$ which are the left and right eigenvectors of $\hat{Q}(0)$ with different eigenvalues $+1$ and -1 , and hence this product must be zero.

5.4 Expressions for the capital growth rates

Consider the capital depending Parrondo's game with p_1, \dots, p_M for the winning probabilities and periodicity M . We find the corresponding \hat{Q} matrix

$$\hat{Q}(\kappa) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & q_2 & \dots & p_M e^{-\kappa} \\ p_1 & 0 & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & p_2 & \cdot & q_M \\ q_1 e^{\kappa} & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (166)$$

Applying the method of [181] gives

$$r = \frac{\sum_i (p_i - q_i) x_i}{\sum_i x_i}. \quad (167)$$

The goal of the game is moving the capital into positive direction. We prove that Eqs. (156,157) give the same result. Let us denote by $\lambda(\kappa)$ the largest eigenvalue of $\hat{Q}(\kappa)$ with left and right eigenstates $\langle y(\kappa) |$ and $|x(\kappa)\rangle$. For $\kappa = 0$ we have $\lambda(0) = 1$ and $\langle y(0) | = (1, 1, \dots, 1)$. The growth rate r is the first derivative of $\log \lambda(\kappa)$ at $\kappa = 0$. As $\lambda(0) = 1$ we have $r = \lambda'(0)$, and

hence

$$r = \frac{\partial}{\partial \kappa} \frac{\langle y(\kappa) | \hat{Q}(\kappa) | x(\kappa) \rangle}{\langle y(\kappa) | x(\kappa) \rangle} = \frac{\langle y(0) | \hat{Q}'(0) | x(0) \rangle}{\langle y(0) | x(0) \rangle}, \quad (168)$$

where the last equality follows from the Hellmann-Feynman theorem. Using the explicit form of the matrix $\hat{Q}(\kappa)$, $\langle y(0) | = (1, 1, \dots, 1)$, and $|x(0)\rangle = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_M)^T$ we find

$$r = \frac{p_M x_M - q_1 x_1}{\sum_i x_i}. \quad (169)$$

Now we prove the equivalence of Eq. (167) and Eq. (169). The eigenvalue equation for the right eigenstate $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_M)^T$ of $\hat{Q}(0)$ for eigenvalue 1 is

$$p_{i-1} x_{i-1} + q_{i+1} x_{i+1} = x_i, \quad (170)$$

for all i . From this we derive

$$p_{i-1} x_{i-1} - q_i x_i = x_i - q_{i+1} x_{i+1} - q_i x_i = p_i x_i - q_{i+1} x_{i+1},$$

where the first equality is simply (170) and the second equality is due to $q_{i+1} = 1 - p_{i+1}$. Hence $p_{i-1} x_{i-1} - q_i x_i$ is independent of i and the sum over this term for all i is simply M times the first term for $i = 1$. The sum over all terms can be written as

$$\sum_i (p_i - q_i) x_i = M(p_0 x_0 - q_1 x_1) = M(p_M x_M - q_1 x_1), \quad (171)$$

where we used the cyclic "boundary condition" $x_0 = x_M$. This completes the proof.

5.5 $M=3$ Parrondo's games

Let us apply the theory of the previous subsection to the concrete case of the $M = 3$ Parrondo's game. We have two elementary games. The first game is a random walk on the 1-d axis with probability h for the right jumps and probability $(1 - h)$ for the left jumps. For the second game the jump parameters depend on the capital value. The probability for the right jumps is h_1 for $\text{mod}(X, 3) \neq 0$ and h_0 for the case $\text{mod}(X, 3) = 0$. We randomly choose the game every round. For this we have an effective $M = 3$ Parrondo's game with probability for right jumps $(h + h_1)/2$ for $\text{mod}(X, 3) \neq 0$ and $(h + h_0)/2$ for the case $\text{mod}(X, 3) = 0$.

We solve the master equation (158) for calculating the probability distribution after t rounds. The results of iterative numerics are given in figures 20 and 21. We see that after $t = 50$ there

Figure 20: The probability distribution for the capital growth $\hat{P}(n, t)$, see Eq. (165), for $t = 50, 100, 150, 200$ for the $M = 3$ Parrondo's model with $p = 0.5 - \epsilon, p_1 = 0.75 - \epsilon, p_2 = 0.1 - \epsilon, \epsilon = 0.005$, [cf. Eq. (172)]. For a proper illustration of the distributions we moved the graphs horizontally. Without this shift, the maximum of the distribution after t rounds is located at the point $n = 0.0052t$. Our analytical results by Eq. (154) are identical to the results of the numerics.

is an oscillation near the maximum, then as time passes the number of oscillations grows.

For the analytic solution with Eqs. (160), (161) we obtain the matrix $\hat{Q}(\kappa)$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & (1 - p_1) & p_2 e^{-\kappa} \\ p_1 & 0 & (1 - p_2) \\ (1 - p_1) e^{\kappa} & p_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (172)$$

where $p_1 = (h + h_0)/2$ and $p_2 = (h + h_1)/2$ are parameters that we choose for the strategies. Let us check it numerically: we have the following three strategies:

- $p_1 = p_2 = h$, for $\text{mod}(X, 3) \neq 0$.
- $p_1 = h_0, p_2 = h_1$, for $\text{mod}(X, 3) \neq 0$,
and the joint strategies
- $p_1 = \frac{h+h_1}{2}, p_2 = \frac{h+h_0}{2}$, for $\text{mod}(X, 3) \neq 0$.

First let us calculate the leading eigenvalue of $\hat{Q}(\kappa)$, namely of Eq. (172), for all three strategies. From this and (168) we determine the (growth) rate r . We find the joint strategy has the opposite sign, which is exactly the parrondo effect. For numerical calculation we take: $h_0 = 0.745, h = 0.495$ and $h_1 = 0.095$. For the fixed values of h_0, h and h_1 we obtain the following expressions for the rate r and the variance K for the corresponding strategies mentioned above:

Figure 21: Illustration of $p(x) = \hat{P}(n, t)$, $x = n/t - r$ with $t = 1000$ for even n (upper two lines) and for the odd n (lower two lines) of the $M = 3$ Parrondo's game with the same parameters as for Figure 20. The smooth lines are derived according to our asymptotic formulas and Eq. (163), the dashed lines correspond to the numerics.

- $r = -0.002898428905$, $K = 0.05281583411$,
- $r = -0.003333333333$, $K = 0.1111111110$,
- $r = 0.005234741795$, $K = 0.09707276331$.

The demonstration of this example shows that two losing strategies may result in a combined strategy, that is winning and exactly this effect is called Parrondo effect. We like to note that in our approach this effect is built on the fact that eigenvalues of a matrix are not linearly dependent on the entries with the trivial exception of the scalar case, see section 5.1. That is why the Parrondo is known as a nonlinear effect.

The $M = 3$ game with zero probability for holding the capital at the current value, has peculiar properties: the probability distribution is non-zero for odd differences in the capital after an odd number of time steps, and for even differences after even time steps. We checked that there are smooth limiting distributions for even and odd n 's, see Figure 21.

We have seen above that strong oscillations exist in the case of zero probability for holding the capital at the current value, $p_l + q_l = 1$. It is interesting and important to understand if this, namely the existence of degenerate saddle points may also appear under other conditions.

Consider the $M = 2$ case. Again, the first game is a random walk on the one dimensional axis with probability p for right jumps and probability q for left jumps. For the second game we have the right jump probabilities p_1, p_2 and left jump probabilities q_1, q_2 . For the random

combination of the games we have the matrix $\hat{Q}(\kappa)$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 - \frac{p_1+q_1+p+q}{2} & \frac{q+q_2}{2} + \frac{p+p_2}{2}e^{-\kappa} \\ \frac{p+p_1}{2} + \frac{q+q_1}{2}e^{\kappa} & 1 - \frac{p_2+q_2+p+q}{2} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (173)$$

5.6 Games with state dependence on history

Consider the case of random walks with memory. We define the current state by (X, α_1, α_2) where X is the current value of the capital, α_1 is $+/-$ if the last change of the capital was gain/loss, and α_2 is $+/-$ if the second last change of the capital was gain/loss. The parameters of the motion are allowed to depend on α_1, α_2 and we get

$$\begin{aligned} P(X, +, \alpha, t+1) &= \sum_{\beta} P(X-1, \alpha, \beta, t)p_{\alpha, \beta}, \\ P(X, -, \alpha, t+1) &= \sum_{\beta} P(X+1, \alpha, \beta, t)(1-p_{\alpha, \beta}). \end{aligned} \quad (174)$$

Let us introduce $w(X, t), y(X, t), z(X, t), h(X, t)$ for the cases $(-, -), (-, +), (+, -), (+, +)$, with corresponding probabilities of the right jumps p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 . Then we have the master equations

$$\begin{aligned} w(X, t+1) &= w(X+1, t)(1-p_1) + z(X+1, t)(1-p_3), \\ y(X, t+1) &= w(X-1, t)p_1 + z(X-1, t)p_3, \\ z(X, t+1) &= y(X+1, t)(1-p_2) + h(X+1, t)(1-p_4), \\ h(X, t+1) &= y(X-1, t)p_2 + h(X-1, t)p_4. \end{aligned} \quad (175)$$

Performing the Fourier transform and subsequent analysis as above we get

$$\begin{aligned} w(X, t) &= v_1 \exp[tu(X/t)], \quad y(X, t) = v_2 \exp[tu(X/t)], \\ z(X, t) &= v_3 \exp[tu(X/t)], \quad h(X, t) = v_4 \exp[tu(X/t)], \end{aligned} \quad (176)$$

where $u(x)$ is obtained from the largest eigenvalue λ of the system of equations

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda v_1 &= (1-p_1)e^{\kappa}v_1 + (1-p_3)e^{\kappa}v_3, \\ \lambda v_2 &= p_1e^{-\kappa}v_1 + p_3e^{-\kappa}v_3, \\ \lambda v_3 &= (1-p_2)e^{\kappa}v_2 + (1-p_4)e^{\kappa}v_4, \\ \lambda v_4 &= p_2e^{-\kappa}v_2 + p_4e^{-\kappa}v_4. \end{aligned} \quad (177)$$

In conclusion, we considered general versions of Parrondo's games. For applications it is

most important to find the capital growth rate and the variance of the distribution. We analyzed not only these characteristics of the models, but also found an exact distribution function. Furthermore, we calculated analytically the asymptotics of the distribution $u(x)$ for large t . The function $u(x)$ satisfies a highly non-linear differential equation, but has an explicit expression as the Legendre transform of a computable function, where for $M > 1$ we have to carry out an eigenvalue analysis. Before our work, the simple matrix $\hat{Q}(0)$ has been used to analyze Parrondo's games [70]. The average growth of the capital is determined by the eigenstate with the maximum eigenvalue 1. Here, we found that the matrix $\hat{Q}(\pi)$ and its eigenvalue -1 lead to fundamental changes of the characteristics of the distribution function. The existence of this eigenvalue creates oscillations in the probability distribution of the capital and results into the existence of two limiting distributions. This is a typical situation with real data of stock fluctuations in financial markets, and it is interesting that our simple model describes this phenomenon. We gave general formulas how to derive the capital growth and variance. The capital growth formula is already known in the literature, the expressions for the variance are rather cumbersome, we just used them numerically.

5.7 Exact probability distribution of the two-envelope problem

The two-envelope problem has attracted researchers and numerous work is devoted to it [184]-[192]. It is a choice between two cases. Such problems related to uncertainty and statistics play an important role in a number of fields including physics, economics, game theory and finally probability theory.

The origin of the problem dates back to [193], where first the “necktie paradox” was presented. Later the important properties of this problem were presented in [194, 195] as the “wallet game”. In 1988 the problem was recast in its present form as the so-called “two-envelope problem” [196]. There are some similarities between the two-envelope game and the “Monty Hall problem” [197, 198], “Newcomb’s paradox” [199] and the “St. Petersburg paradox” [23], but of course it contains some distinguishable features.

In the two-envelope problem, the symmetry is also preserved if the envelopes are closed; broken when the envelopes are opened and an observation is being made [80]. The two-envelope problem has been explored showing interesting similarities with volatility pumping on the stock market, modeling statistical distribution of words in a human language, language of information theory and quantum game setting [80], for the Schroedinger version of the game see [200]. The two-envelope problem possesses counterintuitive dynamics as a result from symmetry breaking in discrete time ratchet phenomenon.

Let us describe it in detail. There are two-envelopes. There is money x in one envelope and $2x$ in the other envelope, where x is obtained from some distribution, $\rho(x)$. In each round, the player randomly chooses an envelope and observes the amount inside. The question is,

should the player keep that envelope or now swap it for the other one, in order to maximize payoff? Using the analogy in [80], if the observed amount is $y \in (x, 2x)$, then the other envelope must contain either $2y$ or $y/2$ dollars. One may be inclined to swap because this will mean either he gains by a net y dollars or drops back by $y/2$ dollars. The same argument holds if the other envelope was selected first, hence we have an apparent paradox [80]. Any apparent paradox is generally due to treating what is actually a conditional probability as an unconditional probability [201]. In this part, we focus on the two-envelope problem attributed by the information theorist Thomas Cover [202]. The amount x is unbounded and there is a large ensemble of independent games.

The average rate of capital has been calculated in [80] and some mathematical results have been derived using functional equations as part of an optimization problem. Here, we will give an integral representation for the exact probability distribution of the model, then calculate both the mean capital growth rate and variance of the capital distribution after a large number of games.

We first assume that the player can either take the money from the envelope that has been opened, or choose another envelope. The choice is described via some probability function, $P(x)$. We need to find the average rate and variance for the player's capital after t rounds, for t large. The rate calculated in [80] makes use of the Cover's switching function [202]. It makes a biased random choice where the bias is conditioned on the observed value of one of the states.

Let us now consider an ensemble of distributions, with probability $p(t, x)$ of having capital x after t trials. When $\rho(x) = \delta(X - x)$,

$$p(t+1, z) = p(t, z - X) \frac{1 - P(X)}{2} + p(t, z - 2X) \frac{P(X)}{2} + \\ + p(t, z - 2X) \frac{1 - P(2X)}{2} + p(t, z - X) \frac{P(2X)}{2}. \quad (178)$$

We use the probabilities $\frac{1-P(X)}{2}$, $\frac{P(X)}{2}$ and $\frac{1-P(2X)}{2}$, $\frac{P(2X)}{2}$ as the player chooses the envelope randomly.

Figure 22 illustrates the scheme for the two-envelope problem as described above, taking into account Eq.(178).

Figure 22: The transition scheme for the two-envelope problem, related to Eq.(178). We show the processes and corresponding probabilities. In the lower boxes, we give the corresponding average change of capital according to Eq.(178).

Similarly, we can obtain the general distribution in the same manner:

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(t+1, z) &= \int dx \rho[x] \left[p(t, z-x) \frac{1-P(x)}{2} + p(t, z-2x) \frac{P(x)}{2} \right. \\
 &+ \left. p(t, z-2x) \frac{1-P(2x)}{2} + p(t, z-x) \frac{P(2x)}{2} \right] = \int dx \rho[x] \left[p(t, z-x) \frac{1-P(x)}{2} \right. \\
 &+ \left. p(t, z-x) \frac{P(2x)}{2} \right] + \int dx \rho[x/2] \left[p(t, z-x) \frac{P(x/2)}{4} + p(t, z-x) \frac{1-P(x)}{4} \right]. \quad (179)
 \end{aligned}$$

We follow the same procedure used in the last section, namely the Fourier transformation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(t, z) &= \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dk e^{iknz} \bar{P}(k, t), \\
 \bar{P}(k, t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int dz P(t, z) e^{-ikz}. \quad (180)
 \end{aligned}$$

We will make use of the analogy between an abundance of money supply and particle to aid in our derivations here. Assume that the particle starts at $n = 0$ and $\bar{P}(k, 0) = \frac{1}{2\pi}$.

Figure 23: The mean capital variance $V(t) \equiv \langle z^2 \rangle - \langle z \rangle^2$ versus time t for the model by Eq.(179) with $X = 1$. The smooth line is given by our numerics using Eq.(179), whereas the solid dots are due to analytics Eq.(187) and a function $P(X)$ with $P(1) = 0.2, P(2) = 0.3$ was used.

Eq.(179) can be easily transformed into

$$\bar{P}(k, t + 1) = e^{tK(-ik)} \bar{P}(k, t), \quad (181)$$

where we denote $p = -ik$,

$$e^{K(p)} = \int dx \rho[x] e^{-px} \left[\frac{1 - P(x)}{2} + \frac{P(2x)}{2} \right] \int dx \rho[x/2] e^{-px} \left[\frac{P(x/2)}{4} + \frac{1 - P(x)}{4} \right]. \quad (182)$$

We can then write the solution as:

$$P(t, z) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk e^{tK(ik) + ikz} \bar{P}(k, 0). \quad (183)$$

Thus, we have obtained an integral representation for the exact probability distribution after t rounds, akin to the solution to Parrondo's games [182]. It will now be useful to calculate the average rate of capital growth and the variance of capital distribution after t rounds to have a better understanding of the process.

Let us use an expansion

$$K(p) = -rp + vp^2/2 + \mathcal{O}(p^3). \quad (184)$$

Eqs. (183) and (184) give

$$r = \int dx \rho[x] x \left[\frac{1 - P(x)}{2} + \frac{P(2x)}{2} \right] \times \\ \times \int dx \rho[x/2] x \left[\frac{P(x/2)}{4} + \frac{1 - P(x)}{4} \right]. \quad (185)$$

Eq.(180) says that r is the average growth rate ($r = \frac{d}{dt} \langle z \rangle$) of capital in the large time limit: after t rounds of the game, the player has a gain rt . In a similar way, we can also derive an expression for v :

$$(r^2 + v) = \int dx \rho[x] x^2 \left[\frac{1 - P(x)}{2} + \frac{P(2x)}{2} \right] + \\ + \int dx \rho\left[\frac{x}{2}\right] x^2 \left[\frac{P(x/2)}{4} + \frac{1 - P(x)}{4} \right]. \quad (186)$$

where $V(t) \equiv vt$ is the variance of the capital distribution after t rounds. For the simple model by Eq.(178), Eqs. (185) and (186) give

$$r = (1.5 - (p_2 - p_1)/2)X \\ v = (0.25 - (p_2 - p_1)^2/4)X^2, \quad (187)$$

where $p_1 \equiv P(X)$, $p_2 = P(2X)$, where the saddle point X turns out to be 1.

Figure 23 depicts the graph for the mean capital variance $V(t) \equiv \langle z^2 \rangle - \langle z \rangle^2$ with respect to time t for the model given by Eq.(179) at $X = 1$, whereas the solid dots are given by Eq.(187), where a function $P(X)$ has been chosen with $P(1) = 0.2$, $P(2) = 0.3$. They are clearly in agreement with each other.

It is not difficult to generalize the model. We can simply choose between two correlated random numbers. When we observe one of them, we naturally obtain information about the second one as well. In such a case, we can construct an algorithm to obtain a better choice among these random assets. We can then formulate the model for the general distribution $\rho(x_1, x_2)$ and minimize the variance.

Conclusion and outlook

6 Conclusion and outlook

In this thesis different systems with many degrees of freedom are investigated. One of the main characteristics of such systems is the “statistical” behavior, which is based on the fact that the system includes uncertainties, randomness and is incompletely defined. Investigations of asymmetries, complexity, stochasticity and non-linearity of such systems were attempted developed in this thesis, which led to various theoretical and empirical analysis of important quantities in the financial and economic world.

There are a number of statistical measurements and tools for random variables. For instance, the investigation of correlation coefficients is a common way to describe the dynamics and dependency between random variables. The moments of the distribution can also describe the phenomenon of interest, but the full investigation can only be achieved if the *probability distribution functions* of the phenomenon are well known, whose analyses are intensively considered in this PhD work, for different systems, by using various methods taken from statistical mechanics.

Since volatility is of major importance in financial sectors such as risk management, portfolio optimization and for the performance of prediction, different studies of it were carried out. The first analysis was based on empirical data without making any model assumptions, which was useful for better understanding the raw data themselves and to approach data-based predictions. As a result of such analyses, a stunning time asymmetry was found between overnight and intraday volatilities. The result is striking and completely unexpected, as far as its significance and robustness are notable.

Intraday volatilities can be considered with higher time resolution (even on the scale of seconds) than overnight volatilities, which consists of just a simple jump. The intraday price fluctuations seem to show a kind of step response pattern. The fact that overnight and next day intraday volatilities are strongly coupled may indicate that intraday volatilities are rather driven by the overnight jumps than by any short term intraday perturbations.

It is known that there is a strong non-linear correlation between price returns [203]. Therefore they can be used for prediction of bursts in time series and associated risk assessment, by using non-linear approaches. This is mostly relevant in cases of a localized breakdown of the symmetry between gain and losses, see [204, 205]. Accordingly the observed strong correlations between overnight and intraday volatilities could lead to an earlier predictability of gains/losses in financial markets, and further improve the risk assessment, giving an earlier Value-at-Risk estimate. It is also challenging to formulate a mechanistic model that allows for an investigation of the distribution function and its volatility by analytic techniques as in [79, 51].

Furthermore the analyses of sentiment and fear index were also addressed here. Such inves-

tigations are useful for forecasting time series (such as Dax and S&P 500 index) which is one of the challenges in finance. The results are interesting and have shown that for example the fear (VIX) index can be a predictor for S&P 500 index, by considering a small time scale and by comparing volatility-VIX correlation and S&P 500 index volatility autocorrelation.

Another investigation was devoted to production processes, as production in real life requires an immense understanding of supportive and inhibitive factors. To this end, a model analysis of the production process was carried through with positive drift and different distribution of noise. The model is based on the experience curve hypothesis, which has been widely used in different domains, such as industrial engineering and operations management services, aimed to estimate the future costs, to reduce the production costs, to evaluate workers' learning profile, etc. It plays also a major role in some strategic tasks such as estimation of capacity, pricing and employment. The concept is also important for the analysis and forecasting of the price drop of products with the number of total products produced, which can lead to the prediction of reduction in cost of manufacture, export potentials of a product can be approximated and the stability of prices can be predicted.

In this thesis potentially powerful analytical and numerical results are found for showing a link between cumulative production and production itself. In the first steps, by use of normally distributed noise in the process a stunning relationship between the volatility of cumulative production and volatility of production itself was found. The results suggest that cumulative production is almost equivalent to an exogenous time trend for predicting technological progress. The evidence and finding is important and our empirical analysis shows how well this model-based finding sets to the dataset, which in turn will allow us to predict the volatility of the cumulative production time series quite well.

In the next step more general types of noise were considered as in industrial activities there exists a large number of cases where the distribution describing a complex phenomenon is not Gaussian. For this variety of applications we found a comprehensive analytical approach, which is based on the arbitrary probability distribution function of the model and which can describe the marketing and movement of production process. We derived a recursion relation of integral type that replaces simulations by highly accurate numerical integration. The results show how different types of noise affect the cumulative production within the model, based on the learning by doing hypothesis. The distribution functions of the volatility are hardly characterized by the mean and variance and show rather interesting, sometimes singular behavior.

Naturally, the cumulative production variables for successive production periods are highly correlated even if noise variables are independent. Another approach shows the occurrence of skewness and kurtosis by non-linear effects. This realizes a rather satisfactory study of the

volatility of cumulative production within the model framework and also shows promising results in the comparative analysis with empirical data.

Our results are valid for arbitrary distribution functions of the production process and yield a systematic control over the validity of the saddle point approximation. Knowing such an important quantity fosters a deeper understanding of the industrial activities. It allows us to also understand the volatile and complex feature of the system and accordingly to calculate the significant quantities, by envisioning the opportunities of the model for future investigations in risk management.

Finally, one of the important findings in this thesis is the exact distribution function for Parrondo's games, which are related to Brownian ratchets and are striking and interesting phenomena at the intersection of multidisciplinary fields. For instance, Luenberger's volatility pumping [82] is one of the simple and similar models to Parrondo's model, which describes nicely the ideas of winning with poorer stocks in a clear way.

Parrondo's paradox is a well-known situation where combinations of losing strategies or harmful effects turn into a winning effect. Over the past decades numerous works reported on the importance and applicability of this phenomena. Parrondo's paradox mostly occurs where non-linearity of stochastic behavior exists in the process. Moreover, Parrondo's paradox awoke an interest in the area of finance [206] because of the existing asymmetry in the model.

For most applications it is critical to find the capital growth rate and the variance of the distribution. Here are calculated not only these characteristics for a variety of models, rather we found the exact probability distribution functions of the model and also the asymptotics of the distribution for large t . This function satisfies a highly non-linear differential equation, but has an explicit expression as the Legendre transform of a quite explicitly known function of the momentum. The tail of the distribution is particularly interesting for applications.

An interesting finding is the existence of oscillations in the probability distribution of the capital after some rounds of gambling. Indications of such oscillations first appeared in the analysis of real financial data, but now in this thesis the phenomenon is found in model systems and a theoretical understanding thereof. Parrondo's games assume a possibility to use a simple switch (degree of mixing between several strategies), either strengthening the system or attenuating it. The latter situation [207] with the possibility of anti-resonance, is typical for the complex enough living systems.

In a similar vein, we have also considered the two-envelope problem and found its exact probability distributions. Probability distribution fitting related to the two-envelope problem can now be carried out for certain phenomena. Predictive analysis can then take place, for instance, to forecast the frequency of occurrence of the magnitude of the phenomenon in a certain interval of interest. It can also be used to obtain the unknown parameters of the

model describing certain data.

7 Appendix

In the Appendix one can find two of the numerical Matlab programs that were used in this thesis. The first program is based on the histogram method for the analysis of mutual information and the second program illustrates the analysis of the mutual information by using K -nearest neighbor statistics.

7.1 Numerical analysis based on histogram method for the estimation of MI

% Estimation of mutual information by using histogram/binning method

```

N=1000;
Nbins=10;

stdwhite=0.5;
nn=100;

xmi=zeros(1,nn);
xa=zeros(1,nn);

for iii=1:100
    a=1/100*iii;
    xa(1,iii)=a;

% create two vector
x=zeros(1,N);
y=zeros(1,N);
% initialize
x(1,1)=rand();
y(1,1)=x(1,1);

for i=1:N-1
    x(1,i+1)=a*x(1,i)+stdwhite*randn(1);
    y(1,i+1)=a*x(1,i);

```

```

end
sxy=zeros(Nbins , Nbins );

hbinsx=(max(x)-min(x))/( Nbins - 1);
hbinsy=(max(y)-min(y))/( Nbins - 1);

for k=1:N
    for i=1:Nbins
        if (x(1 , k)>=min(x)+hbinsx*(i - 1)) && (x(1 , k)<min(x)+hbinsx*(i ))
            ki=i ;
        end
    end
    for j=1:Nbins
        if (y(1 , k)>=min(y)+hbinsy*(j - 1)) && (y(1 , k)<min(y)+hbinsy*(j ))
            kj=j ;
        end
    end
    sxy(kj , ki)=sxy(kj , ki)+1;
end
jprob=sxy/sum(sum(sxy ));

MI=0;
for i=1:Nbins
    for j=1:Nbins
        if (jprob(i , j)>0)
            MI=MI+jprob(i , j)*log2((jprob(i , j)/
                (sum(jprob(i , :))*sum(jprob(: , j)))));
        end
    end
end

end
xmi(1 , i i i)=MI;
end

plot(xa , xmi)

```

7.2 Numerical analysis based on KNN statistics for the estimation of MI

% Estimation of mutual information using K nearest neighbor statistics

% determine constants

N=1000;

K=5;

nn=100;

% B=zeros(1,N);

xmi=**zeros**(1,nn);

xa=**zeros**(1,nn);

for iii=1:100

 a=1/100*iii;

 xa(1,iii)=a;

% time series

x=**zeros**(1,N);

y=**zeros**(1,N);

% initialize

x(1,1)=**rand**();

y(1,1)=x(1,1);

for i=1:N-1

 x(1,i+1)=a*x(1,i)+0.5***randn**();

 y(1,i+1)=a*x(1,i);

end

% calculate all distances from each point

for i=1:N

```

for j=1:N

    if i~=j

        ep_x_temp(1,i)=abs(x(1,i)-x(1,j));
        ep_y_temp(1,j)=abs(y(1,i)-y(1,j));
        ep_temp(i,j)=max(ep_x_temp(1,i),ep_y_temp(1,j));

    end

end

end

nx=zeros(1,N);
ny=zeros(1,N);
ep=zeros(1,N);

for i=1:N
    Brow=ep_temp(i,:);
    B=sort(Brow);
    B(:,1)=[];
    ep(1,i)=B(1,K-1);

for T=1:N

    if ( abs(x(1,i)-x(1,T)))<ep(1,i)

        nx(1,i)=nx(1,i)+1;

    end

```

```

    if ( abs(y(1,i)-y(1,T))) < ep(1,i)

        ny(1,i)=ny(1,i)+1;
    end

end

end

end

%      using second estimator for MI

sum_n=0;
for i=1:N

    if nx(1,i)~=0 && ny(1,i)~=0

        sum_n= (psi(nx(1,i))+psi(ny(1,i)))+sum_n;
    end

end

MI=psi(K)-1/K-(1/N)*(sum_n)+psi(N);
xmi(1, i i)=MI;

end

plot(xa,xmi)

```

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